

Argumentation training against undemocratic slogans:
European extension and updating
ref. No 2023-2-DE04-KA220-YOU-000175190

Exchange & Best Practices

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

standup4.eu

Stand Up for Europe

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May 2025

Typesetting and Design: Doğa Schools Projects Coordinatorship

ISBN: 978-625-8178-89-0

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

The Stand Up for Europe (Argumentation training against undemocratic slogans: European extension and updating) project is funded by the European Union through the Erasmus+ KA220-YOU Cooperation Partnerships in Youth Programme. However, the views and opinions expressed in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union or the European Agency for Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for this situation.

Preface

This document offers a comparative exploration of argumentation training and values education across five European countries, conducted within the framework of the Stand Up for Europe project. It seeks to contribute to the development of innovative educational tools that empower youth workers to effectively counter anti-democratic narratives and foster a culture of civic dialogue. By drawing on national insights, research findings, and exemplary practices, the report provides both a conceptual foundation and a practical inspiration for strengthening democratic engagement among young people. Its purpose is to serve as a catalyst for future pedagogical innovation rooted in European values.

Intellectual Output Details

Program: Erasmus+ KA220-YOU Cooperation Partnerships in Youth

Project Reference Number: 2023-2-DE04-KA220-YOU-000175190

Project Acronym: Stand Up for Europe

Project Title: Stand Up for Europe! Argumentation Training Against Undemocratic Slogans: European Extension and Updating

Project Timeframe: 01/03/2024 - 28/02/2026

Intellectual Output Number: WP2

Version: 1.0

Completion Date: May 2025

Publication Date: May 2025

Project Coordinator: Groupe SOS Solidarités

Lead Partner: Doğa Schools

Contributed Partners: Akademie Klausenhof GmbH, Catholic Youth Foundation, Universität Augsburg, Socialna Akademija, InEuropa SRL

Website: www.standup4.eu

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1. Partners

Akademie Klausenhof GmbH (Coordinator, Germany)

akademie-klausenhof.de

The Klausenhof Academy is an international education and training centre for young people and adults in Hamminkeln and Rhede. The Klausenhof Academy offers courses in (rehabilitation-specific) initial training for disabled and unemployed adults, language courses and further qualification courses, integration courses for young migrants, courses in German as a foreign language, seminars and workshops (focus: political education, youth work, professional training, management) as well as international, European and regional projects. It operates with its projects and offers both locally and regionally as well as nationally and internationally.

It is a recognized provider of youth welfare (inpatient and outpatient). Every day, around 600 to 1000 people visit the various offers of the house. Around half of these are young people and young adults. The Klausenhof Academy has 600 boarding school places and 350 employees. It is a non-profit GmbH under the sponsorship of a Catholic foundation and is certified according to DIN EN ISO 9001:2015.

Catholic Youth Foundation (Hungary)

katolikusifjusagialapitvany.hu

The Catholic Youth Foundation (CYF) was founded in 1991 in Szeged to support the education and community activities of Catholic youth in Southern Hungary. The Foundation carries out wide-ranging activities in the region to promote Christian values and to form a vibrant and authentic community of young adults. The Foundation focuses its activities on the following main tasks: Youth work - Youth work has always been at the heart of our mission. We have used the following main tools to realize innovative and widespread youth work in the Southern Region: Organization of cultural programs - The Foundation's mission is to promote and preserve Christian and Hungarian values in the Southern Hungary region. The "Millenniumi" café in the city centre serves this purpose. In the 20 years of its activity, 3000 programs and events with 150 000 participants have been organized.

Social activities and volunteer work - Since the beginning of its activity, the Catholic Youth Foundation has had a mission to develop society, support disadvantaged groups and promote voluntary activities. For the last 20 years, the Millennium Café, operated under the supervision of CYF, has been the main base for cultural dissemination in Szeged. CYF has organized summer music festivals for several years (Millennium Jazz Days, Millennium Blues Session since 2014, Dugonics Square Summer Festival since 2006, participating in the Szeged Day celebrations).

Universität Augsburg (Germany)

Universität
Augsburg
University

uni-augsburg.de

The University of Augsburg was founded in 1970 as a reform university by the Free State of Bavaria. Initially focusing on law, economics, social sciences and humanities, the University of Augsburg has steadily expanded into promising fields such as natural and technical sciences and medicine. Its 20,000 students participate in around 40 undergraduate and state examination courses and 50 advanced master's courses. With numerous partnerships and cooperation agreements with over 80 universities worldwide and around 320 Erasmus exchange agreements, the University of Augsburg has a strong international network in both research and teaching. Centres currently being established at the university include the focus areas "European Studies" and "Teaching/Learning Research".

In keeping with its motto "Scientia et Conscientia", the University of Augsburg strives to increase, acquire and preserve knowledge in a conscientious and socially responsible manner and is committed to unrestricted freedom of research and teaching. The aim of its teaching is the ability to learn scientifically and to independently acquire scientific methods and knowledge. It encourages and demands that students learn and act independently. The course contributes to the development of mature, critical, responsible citizens who are committed to democratic values.

Doğa Schools (Türkiye)

dogakoleji.k12.tr

Doğa Schools is a chain of private schools, manages 90 campuses all around Türkiye and 1 in Cyprus, and educates 80000 students with its 7500 staff members. Based on these figures and the extensive network it has, Doğa Schools has an unrivalled potential to reach students, parents, educators, civil servants and stakeholders in national and international education field and also to disseminate across a broad area. Doğa schools enjoy a close relationship with various regional education departments in Türkiye and are therefore able to involve state schools to the projects as well.

Doğa Schools aims to provide pupils with competencies that they can become multi-directional, participative, creative and sensitive individuals of the future. The teaching and the management staff are actively engaged in the development and implementation of innovative teaching concepts such as MBA for teenagers (t-MBA), Project Based High School Education and Natural Learning Concept (NLC).

Doğa Schools serve for school education from pre-school to high school (3-18 years of age) to follow the curricular changes, improve the teacher training programmes, develop learning objects and online educational tools through collaborating with national stakeholders (provincial directorates, municipalities, universities, and NGOs) and international partners and stakeholders (universities, NGOs, and schools) and actively engaged in development and implementation of innovative teaching concepts.

Socialna Akademija (Slovenia)

socialna-akademija.si

Socialna Akademija (Social Academy) is a non-profit institute operating since 2004 with activities in the fields of education, research and culture. The mission of the Social Academy is to promote, through education, training, research and promotion, a culture based on common values such as respect for human dignity, solidarity, justice and the common good, contributing to active citizenship and social responsibility of youth and young adults.

In the field of youth work, the Social Academy promotes active citizenship and media literacy, develops non-formal training of youth leaders and workers, offers activities in the field of multimedia production in its own multimedia centre and promotes intergenerational cooperation. Some recent international projects: Hard Topics, Creative Digital Spaces, ABC of youth work (applicant), European Wide Web of youth work, TeachHear, ILEAC, Young Faces of Europe, Enjoy Your Rights, Youth Worker and MotivAction.

InEuropa SRL (Italy)

progettareineuropa.com

InEuropa SRL is an Italian company founded in 2006 by experts who have been working on EU projects for more than 20 years, with the aim of helping public and private entities to access European innovation actions. InEuropa provides information, training and advice on EU policies and programs, promotes knowledge and interest in European opportunities and helps to develop transnational projects by providing technical support in both the planning and management phases. In addition to information and advisory services, InEuropa participates in its own European projects, either as a partner or as a coordinator. Education, training, youth, culture, environment, social, health, research and innovation are the main areas of work. In this framework, various projects aim to increase knowledge and awareness of environmental challenges and behavioural change and to develop experimental non-formal training pathways aimed at schools, young people and adults.

InEuropa has extensive experience in managing projects and developing training methods in the fields of education and training, behaviour change, culture and integration. InEuropa tests various non-formal training methods with young people and adults to promote their personal and professional growth, help them identify goals and reflect on the impact of their lifestyle on the world.

2. Authors

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Dr Zuhal Yılmaz Doğan is Doğa Schools' Projects Coordinator. She contributed to the development of on-line courses and coordinated project activities in schools in LLP Projects bsiproject.com, ntse-nanotech.eu, sustain-project.eu. She has extended experience as a foreign language teacher and as a teacher-trainer for the Ministry of National Education, training language teachers on current methodologies and programs, as well as on instructional design for interdisciplinary teaching. She researched the applicability of A CEF-R for Languages in public schools as part of her master study and gained a PhD at Yıldız Technical University of Program Design and Development Department. She obtained a TESOL certificate from the University of Massachusetts in 2011.

Umur Bakkal (Doğa Schools, Türkiye)

Umur Bakkal is Doğa Schools' EU Projects Expert. He received his Bachelor's degree in International Affairs and is studying for his Master's degree in European Politics and International Affairs at Marmara University. In addition to carrying out international projects in the scope of EU funding programs, he participates in the training of students and teachers and academic guidance of scientific research project competitions at national and international levels. His professional interests are innovative approaches to education and gender equality, combating climate change, projects prioritising accessibility with high-quality digitalisation and studies on European policies. He participates in various NGOs acting in the fields of environment, human rights and freedoms.

Danny Arati (Doğa Schools, Türkiye)

Danny Arati is an External Consultant for Doğa Schools and has contributed extensively to a number of EU-funded projects focused on a variety of educational themes. He brings in-depth expertise in educational technology, particularly at the intersection of digital tools and cognitive processes in the classroom. His work has centred on the development of innovative, assessment-for-learning solutions and the advancement of contemporary teaching and learning methodologies. In addition to content development, he has played a key role in designing and delivering targeted teacher training programmes.

Dr Michael Sommer (Akademie Klausenhof, Germany)

Dr Michael Sommer is a specialist journalist for educational topics and was editor of the magazine "*Erwachsenenbildung*" (Adult Education) for more than 20 years. He also works for European media and has been organising European education projects for many years.

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Elisa Lai graduated in Foreign Languages and International Relations (political studies involving Human Rights and International Law), Elisa Lai is specifically skilled in project design, research, information delivery and project technical implementation.

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Eva Gajšek (Socialna Akademija, Slovenia)

Eva Gajšek holds a university degree as a professor of Slovenian language and theology (VII). She also holds a national vocational qualification as a youth worker. She has worked as a project manager at the Social Academy since 2017, where she focuses on projects related to youth employment and active citizenship.

Among her notable contributions, she worked on the “European Parliament Ambassador School” project (2016-2019), was a coworker on the national project “Inkubator 4.0” (2017-2018 and 2020-2021) and participated in the regional project “Inkubator 4.0” in the City Municipality of Ljubljana (2019-2025). She is currently working on a national project titled “DD – Dostojno delo” (Decent Work) which educates youth workers on the consequences of precariousness and how to address these issues among young people.

Matej Cepin (Socialna Akademija, Slovenia)

Matej Cepin, director of the Social Academy, has been involved in non-formal education and youth work for over 25 years and is an internationally recognized trainer in these fields. His clients include the National Agency of Erasmus+ program, some major NGOs in the country and various public institutions. He is also the author or editor of several publications focusing on youth work, educational methods, career guidance, adult education, personal development and active/responsible citizenship. He also holds a university degree as an Engineer in Computer Science and Informatics (VII).

From 2019 to 2022, he was the project manager of the “Inkubator Solidarnosti,” where he supported social initiatives and developed support systems. From 2016 to 2018, he led the “ABC of Youth Work” project, which focused on developing a quality system for integrating marginalized youth into permanent groups. Currently, he is leading a project “Hard Topics” that focuses on the dialogue between different social groups.

3. Introduction & Project Summary

The *Stand Up for Europe* project aims to increase the quality, innovation, and recognition of youth work, and to promote active citizenship, young people's sense of initiative, and youth entrepreneurship—including social entrepreneurship—to enable people to effectively embrace European values. Another goal of the *Stand Up for Europe* project is updating and Europeanising a proven argumentation training, *Training Against Regular Table Slogans*, and spreading it to other European countries.

Within the second output of the project, titled *Exchange and Best Practice*, the aim is to identify and implement European common values and their existing references, including methods of raising awareness and communicating values. The scientific results and approaches obtained in various studies, as well as the prominent experiences, models, and comparable tools in the countries of the practical project partner organisations, have been investigated, and the foundations laid for updating and expanding the argumentation training programme. One such method is the *Training Against Regular Table Slogans* argumentation technique developed by Klaus-Peter Hufer. As part of updating and adapting this training for wider use across Europe, it is essential to define key concepts, including “argumentation techniques” and “table slogans.”

Based on the context prepared and disseminated by *WP2 Exchange and Best Practice*, a training tool will be developed by the *Stand Up for Europe* project consortium to help teachers and experts working in youth education improve their methodological skills. The content also includes various successful methods researched and provided by partners, along with argumentation training methodologies.

Exchange and Best Practice gathers the partners' reports on the national landscape surrounding argumentation training and values education in their countries, as part of developing an educational training tool to improve skills for youth workers in countering anti-democratic rhetoric. Existing initiatives in partners' countries related to Klaus-Peter Hufer's argumentation techniques against table slogans or comparable methods have been summarised in national reports and combined into a joint report.

The national reports detail how such training aligns with proposed EU values around civil debate and democratic principles, and provide target demographics for this training, such as youth aged 13–30. Additionally, partners were provided with two best practice examples of effective educational models for teaching argumentation methods relevant to promoting European values.

The goal of *WP2 Exchange and Best Practice* is to collect effective approaches, target groups, and best practices from diverse national contexts across Europe to inform the creation of the *Stand Up for Europe* educational training tool. This tool aims to expand the scope of youth programmes offered to counter the spread of hate speech, fake news, exclusionary populism, and anti-democratic views—helping teach peaceful debate, inclusion, and democratic values.

The contents prepared by the partner organisations as a result of their research in their countries (Germany, Hungary, Italy, Slovenia, and Türkiye) were collected by Doğa Schools, the leader of this work package, and the consolidated findings turned into a brochure, which is to be published in all partner languages (DE, PL, HU, TR, SL). In addition to these, the brochure is prepared to be a stepping stone for the development of *Stand Up for Europe* project intellectual outputs titled *WP3 Handbook/Curriculum: Stand Up for Europe for Educational Practice*, which will be prepared with the aim of boldly bringing various counter-arguments against extremist and stereotypical slogans into debate—concretely updating and expanding existing argumentation training against standard table slogans—and *WP4 Online Learning Tool*, an online learning tool based on the results of previous intellectual outputs and a serious game/gamification principle, aiming to digitally extend argumentation education.

4. Hufer's Antidemocratic Slogans

Klaus Peter Hufer defines *Stammtischparolen* (typically prejudiced catchphrases and stereotypes heard in social settings like drinking establishments, somewhat akin to antidemocratic slogans) as exaggerated, racist, populist, discriminatory, and sexist statements based on half-truths that spread negative prejudices. (Hufer, 2020). These slogans categorise groups of people, divide the world into "them" and "us", and offer simple answers to complex societal issues. Common examples blame foreigners, refugees, Jews, Muslims, the EU, politicians, etc., for problems in society (Hufer, 2020). Table slogans propagate racism, discrimination, xenophobia, and authoritarian views. Examples include blaming foreigners, minorities, politicians, etc., for societal problems.

Hufer argues that while table slogans are simplistic, it is difficult to spontaneously refute them, as they fulfil a dual function—they are both aggressive and a source of self-affirmation for those who proclaim them. Additionally, logical argumentation is often ineffective, as table slogans are not grounded in reason but rather in "fundamental value judgments, beliefs and principles" (Hufer, 2020).

Nevertheless, Hufer provides recommendations for countering table slogans, which he terms "argumentation techniques". Klaus Peter Hufer's core argumentation technique involves avoiding escalation, asking probing questions, addressing emotions, and redirecting conversations to sway undecided onlookers. These include avoiding being drawn into slogan debates, taking the initiative in the discussion, establishing rules for dialogue, asking specific questions to elicit details, insisting listeners truly listen, positioning yourself based on ethics and values, revealing contradictions in the slogans, using Socratic questioning, addressing the emotions behind the slogans, and refocusing on undecided bystanders who may be convinced by strong counter-arguments. The goal is not just to win an argument but to demonstrate a steadfast yet understanding democratic attitude. Verbal disarmament is key, as table slogans can lead to physical violence. The aim is to speak out in an appropriate yet upright manner, to demonstrate that democracy still allows dissenting voices (Hufer, 2020).

5. Current State of Argumentation Training in Partners' Countries

Chapter 5 briefly presents the current status of argumentation training in *Stand Up for Europe* Project Consortium partners' countries by using existing national education/development programmes or strategic documents, activities carried out by initiatives, articles and reports of various institutions or researchers, or project examples, covering the project's target groups.

The chapter respectively includes partner countries' context regarding argumentation training and European values; an overview of existing programmes, initiatives, or projects; the target groups and participants (aged between 13–30); and the methodologies and approaches used, as well as challenges and opportunities faced in implementing argumentation training or comparable methods.

5.1 The Case of Germany

In Germany, the promotion of democracy has been an integral part of schools, extracurricular educational work, and adult education—at least since the end of the Nazi era. The Western 'occupying powers' played a major role in this, initiating an extensive programme of re-education and thus laying the foundations for an institutionally, conceptually, and methodologically comprehensive education on democracy. It is called *political education* (*Politische Bildung*) in German. The term is somewhat problematic, as it can also refer to education and upbringing in the sense of a particular policy or worldview and to propaganda or indoctrination. For this reason, the English-speaking world uses the term *citizenship education*, i.e. education to become active, informed, and committed citizens.

As Germany is organised as a federal state, the individual federal states determine the specific education policy. The comprehensive term *social studies* (*Sozialkunde*) or *politics* (*Politik*) has become established as a school subject. In addition to other subjects such as economics, this subject can also include *political education* or *civics* (*Staatsbürgerkunde*). Recently, there have also been repeated efforts to place the constitutional values at the centre of interactive discussions in the school context. In the 2024/2025 school year, for example, Bavaria introduced a 'constitutional quarter hour', in which individual values of the Bavarian constitution are discussed and linked to one's own lived experience.

However, *political education* is not only practiced in schools. Due to the importance of embedding liberal-democratic principles in society as a whole, separate organisations were set up in Germany after the war, from 1952 onwards, at both federal and state level to promote democracy through education—that is, also outside schools (Caruso, Schatz 2018). In Germany, these activities are known as *extracurricular political education* (*außerschulische politische Bildung*) and *adult political education* (*politische Erwachsenenbildung*). There is a state-funded but independent "Federal Agency for Political Education" (*Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung*) and a "State Agency for Political Education" (*Landeszentrale für politische Bildung*) in each federal state. These institutions not only produce relevant (educational) materials, create publications, and organise courses, but are also often present in public discourse as representatives and advocates of democratic principles.

The activities are primarily aimed at adolescents and young people but include people at all stages of life. Experts, teachers, and educational organisations are addressed, as is the target group directly via events, projects, workshops, and other activities. In the context of extracurricular citizenship education, the terms 'learning democracy' or 'democracy as a way of life' are often used to emphasise the non-indoctrination, open-process nature of this kind of education. While political didactics at universities is essentially characterised by political science in the school sector, the reference sciences for extracurricular citizenship education are often educational science and sociology.

Educational institutions outside schools that provide citizenship education are usually financially supported by the state through "continuing education laws". The provider landscape is diverse and ranges from municipal adult education centres to institutions organised by trade unions or churches. Germany has a very varied and differentiated system of education outside traditional initial education such as schools or universities (Sander 2022).

Discussion of values in Germany – Basic Law

Political education primarily refers to the values set out in the German Basic Law. These are usually described using terms such as "liberal", "social" or "democratic". The Basic Law was created in the wake of the crimes of the Nazi dictatorship and is based on the experiences of Western democracies.

It sets out absolute values (e.g. human dignity, freedom), as well as values and norms that the state must uphold in relation to its citizens (e.g. privacy, freedom of religion).

The value system of the Basic Law provides a framework for orientation, but also offers plenty of room for flexibility, contradictions and potential for development. New technologies and social developments require new regulations, for example in the areas of environmental protection or asylum.

In principle, the values outlined in the Basic Law can also be described as “European values”. However, it is much more difficult to identify a universally valid “European” catalogue of values from the many different European documents.

In addition to the normative aspect of (political) values, the reality and implementation of values at various levels must be considered: by citizens themselves, by civil society, political parties, the media and academia, as well as by those in power and in the economy. The more recent focus on value formation mentioned above aims to highlight the different prioritisation of certain values, the contradictions and dilemmas between values, and thus the responsibility of everyone to make value-based decisions. This is also intended to promote understanding of openness, complexity and enduring challenges of democratic political processes.

This National Report presents the debate on values in Germany and how they are addressed in political education in general, and in argumentation training in particular.

Argumentation training against *Stammtischparolen* (antidemocratic slogans)

Background

This diversity is also reflected in the “Argumentation training against antidemocratic slogans” programme. Klaus-Peter Hufer developed, implemented and has continuously improved the curriculum since 2000 as a practitioner and head of department at a municipal adult education centre. He remains active today as a trainer and lecturer throughout Germany, organising around two events per week (Deutscher Volkshochschulverband n.d.). He has also trained other trainers who now use the programme themselves. Various universities in Germany (in particular Essen/Duisburg, Cologne and Augsburg) are involved with the training programme, having developed quality criteria and enhancements, and conducted related studies.

Demand for the programme has risen sharply, particularly due to political events (e.g. the AfD’s entry into the Bundestag, Trump’s election in the USA, etc.).

What is argumentation training against antidemocratic slogans? The inventor Klaus-Peter Hufer describes it as follows:

“Argumentation training against antidemocratic slogans” is a special case of argumentation training in that it involves dealing with conflictual encounters that are politically explosive. In this argumentation training, political education takes place – initiated and developed by everyone together. Rhetorical skills are also learnt and practised, but it is not just empty rhetorical training. The participants’ self-confidence is also strengthened, but it is not an individualising seminar for self-awareness.” (Deutscher Volkshochschulverband n.d.).

Hufer defines *Stammtischparolen* (antidemocratic slogans) as “unambiguous ideological, preferably political messages, in favour of flat slogans and aggressive dogmatism” (Deutscher Volkshochschulverband n.d.).

Method

The aim of the training is to learn techniques for countering provocative, racist and undemocratic slogans in specific situations involving personal encounters and confrontation. Various techniques are practised through role-play, such as counter-questions or the use of irony. For example, typical positions of conspiracy theorists, overt or covert racism and anti-Semitism, misogyny, or anti-European prejudices are discussed. These positions may be loud, provocative, hurtful, illegal and obvious – as well as subtle and even unconscious. The spectrum ranges from statements such as “All politicians should be gassed” to seemingly innocuous slogans and jokes like “Women can’t park”.

The courses therefore also aim to teach participants to recognise such anti-democratic statements in the first place, to identify the underlying values, and to summon the courage to take a stand against them using arguments. Finally, participants are encouraged to critically reflect on their own attitudes to avoid the appearance of arrogance.

Hufer outlines the following strategies in his book:

- Stick to one topic; don't just touch on various issues like buzzwords
- Take the initiative
- Establish rules for dialogue
- Make targeted enquiries
- Compelling others to listen
- Avoid lecturing
- Do not moralise
- Take a clear stance
- Avoid generalisations about groups of people (e.g. "foreigners")
- Clarify problems
- Expose contradictions
- Ask questions
- Distract and de-escalate
- Address emotions
- Build bridges
- Set boundaries
- Change perspectives
- Pay attention to the undecided
- Remain authentic
- Use humour and irony
- Lower expectations
- Consider long-term impact

The training is primarily aimed at individuals who are already politically engaged or willing to become so. It is not designed to convert those using such slogans or to motivate a disinterested group. Accordingly, it is most often requested by clubs, associations, extracurricular educational institutions, NGOs, political parties, churches, community groups and other civil society organisations. For instance, workshops have been conducted for particular migrant groups, trade union organisations, and Catholic parishes. The main target groups are young people aged 16 and over, as well as adults.

Of course, there are many other approaches and training programmes in this field – some are modified versions of Hufer's argumentation training, while others follow different concepts across the German-speaking world, including strategies for dealing with fake news and online abuse. An overview of the key publications on this topic is provided at the end of this chapter. In addition, three further best practice examples are presented below.

Effectiveness

Are such training programmes even effective, and can they make a difference? The question of effectiveness or evidence is not easily answered in the field of education. In principle, possible effects

operate on three levels – knowledge, attitude and action – and can vary in both the short and long-term depending on the target group.

In political education, and especially in argumentation training, a wide range of effects is conceivable: strengthening and consolidating commitment, increasing motivation, decoding populist language, encouraging self-reflection, boosting self-confidence, improving communication skills, acquiring strategic knowledge, changing attitudes, and raising awareness. These learned skills may be applied immediately (e.g. at the next birthday party), become ingrained personality traits over time, or contribute to wider societal impact, such as influencing elections or enhancing general democratic engagement.

However, such indicators of effectiveness are usually difficult or even impossible to operationalise in research. This type of educational work is therefore typically grounded in a general commitment to defending democracy on the part of both providers and most participants. This is especially true for groups made up of voluntary participants. The situation may differ with groups such as school classes.

Nevertheless, studies suggest that the training positively influences motivation, strategic knowledge and the quality of argumentation (see Reinfeldt 2013; Ahlheim & Heger 2006; Gronostay 2019; Zeuner & Pabst 2020).

Target groups

More precise conclusions about the structure of the target group (young, politically engaged people and representatives of minorities) can be drawn from research into the political behaviour and values of the population. This also includes a look at the group of people who use populist or anti-democratic slogans.

Primary target group: politically and socially engaged people

Argumentation training is primarily aimed at people who are prepared to stand up for democracy and human rights. These may be “professionals” involved in political debate and decision-making, such as those active in political parties, civil rights movements, interest groups, associations, clubs, the media or other organisations. Those who are active on social media and publish posts are also likely to be considered politically interested. The second subgroup comprises those who are “interested” but not necessarily “active”. Good argumentation training can turn interested people into active participants and further strengthen the commitment of those already involved.

According to the renowned Shell Study from 2019, 8% of young people in Germany describe themselves as politically active and a further 33% as politically interested. The EU is viewed positively by 43%, and very positively by 7%, while 7% have a negative or very negative (1%) image of the EU. Freedom of movement, a Europe without borders, cultural diversity and democracy in Europe are particularly important to them. The study formed five “populism category” clusters. They show that around a third support European democratic values, while another third are undecided. A third of young people also lean towards populist tendencies:

- **Cosmopolitans:** 39%
 - **Populism learners:** 24%
 - **National populists:** 9%
 - **Not clearly positioned:** 28%
- (Albert, Hurlimann, & Quenzel, Kantar / Shell Study 2019)

Secondary target group: people with “group-focused enmity”

German researchers have described and scientifically demonstrated the syndrome of group-focused misanthropy (GMF) in the book *Deutsche Zustände*. The GMF syndrome comprises 13 elements: racism, xenophobia, antisemitism, hostility towards Muslims, sexism, devaluation of certain groups such as Sinti and Roma, asylum seekers, homosexuals, trans people, homeless people, the long-term unemployed and people with disabilities (Zick, Küpper, & Berghan 2019, 58 ff.; Heitmeyer 2024).

The individual categories of the GMF syndrome correspond to the statements commonly found in antidemocratic slogans, which Hufer’s argumentation training addresses.

As already seen in the values of young people (see above), around 30% of Germans are populist, although they mostly hold moderate positions. Global criticism of the “establishment” and mainstream media is particularly widespread, although the majority of this group do not call for radical change, but rather certain adjustments. A majority (37%) of respondents in the study reject populist attitudes. According to the study, populism in Germany “is to be categorised as moderate rather than radical”. For example, more than two-thirds of people with populist attitudes support EU membership and 85% approve of the democratic system. However, over three-quarters believe that EU integration has gone too far, and a narrow majority of 52% believe that democracy “does not work well” or “does not work at all” in Germany (Vehrkamp & Wratil 2017).

A European comparison also yields similar figures: in Germany, 18% stated that they agreed with the positions of the right-wing populist party *Alternative für Deutschland (AfD)*. In Poland, by contrast, the figure is 78%, in France 63%, and in the Netherlands 55% (Twyman 2016).

Conspiracy theorists

The studies mentioned above were mainly conducted from 2015 onwards – motivated by the rise of right-wing populism and the election of Donald Trump as President of the USA. The coronavirus pandemic has triggered a new wave of populism that, like right-wing populism, is marked by an anti-scientific stance and opposition to the (political) establishment and European politics: the “conspiracy theorists”. According to a recent study, 30% of Germans believe that the world is controlled by secret powers. This proportion is particularly high among voters of the right-wing populist Alternative for Germany (AfD) party. Around 13% of Germans are convinced that the coronavirus is a Chinese bioweapon. In contrast, 46% of the population believe these theories are entirely fabricated, while 40% believe they contain a kernel of truth, even if not everything is accurate. Conversely, the proportion of Germans who view conspiracy theories as a growing threat to democracy is high, at 66% (Statista Research Department 2024).

These statistics clearly show that in a group of 30 people – such as a school class or at a birthday party – statistically speaking, at least 10 individuals are likely to be right-wing populists or conspiracy theorists. Three of them may hold radical convictions. The group that is democratically oriented is just as large. Of these, three are so committed and interested that they would actively argue against undemocratic and anti-scientific statements. Ten other people in the group are indifferent to the issue. This also means that the above-mentioned categories of group-focused misanthropy are likely to affect certain marginalised or discriminated groups in everyday interactions within any such group.

5.2 The Case of Hungary

Since the change of regime, Hungary has had a two-pole curriculum management system (previously, centralised management was the norm). This means that both central and local decisions prevail in matters of planning (objectives, content selection, curriculum design). This system regulates the education of students in primary and secondary schools up to the age of 18. After the change of regime, Hungarian curriculum regulation became three-tiered (Perjés & Vass, 2008).

The top-level regulation is the National Core Curriculum, which was issued by the Hungarian Government in 2012 and last modified in 2020. The basic curriculum defines the mandatory common objectives of educational work within the framework of general education. It interprets the so-called key competences adopted in the European Union for public education in Hungary, lays the foundation for the quality management tasks related to the basic curriculum, and includes, in particular, the development tasks to be implemented in the individual content phases, which form the basis of the educational work.

The second level is the framework curriculum, which plays a mediating role between the local curriculum and the National Core Curriculum. The local curriculum is the third level. It is selected and drawn up in accordance with the objectives and principles of a school's pedagogical programme. Its local character stems from the fact that it is legitimised by the agreement of local stakeholders, the acceptance of the board of governors, the supportive opinion of various users and partners, and the approval of the maintainer. A secondary, but not insignificant, feature is that it incorporates elements of local culture to an acceptable extent. By local culture, we mean both the traditions and the vision of local society (Venkovits & Makay, 2022).

In 2002, Hunya examined the National Core Curriculum, the framework curriculum and the available textbooks to determine to what extent they offered opportunities for the use or teaching of debate and argumentation in Hungarian schools. In the study, Hunya concluded that these key documents require the development of debate and argumentation skills at several points. He also argued that debates help to implement the core values and principles of the curriculum and to meet the requirements (Hunya, 2002a, 2002b).

In 2017, Tibor Oláh also examined this issue and concluded that the National Core Curriculum considers the use and teaching of debate and argumentation important, while at the same time drawing attention to the difficulties of implementing the principles of the National Core Curriculum and the Framework Curriculum. With few textbooks, manuals and training sessions available to help teachers acquire the necessary skills to conduct classroom debates, teachers are left to deal with the issue alone. It was felt that teachers would either learn argumentation techniques and debate formats on their own, or they would not be able to adequately develop students' relevant skills (Oláh, 2017).

According to Venkovits and Makay's analysis, the National Curriculum and the framework curricula explicitly recommend the use of debates in a number of subjects, such as foreign languages, history, civic studies, biology and geography. The research concludes that the Hungarian regulatory system provides a sufficient basis for debate-based education and for the acquisition of good reasoning skills. However, the research also finds that the regulatory system does not provide methodological support to teachers, which prevents them from effectively integrating debates into everyday teaching. The surveys presented in this study show that few practising teachers and teacher trainees are aware of how to apply debate- and argumentation-based teaching in their daily work. However, the researchers suggest that this can be overcome with appropriate training and methodological support for teachers and teacher trainees. They find that, during secondary school years, students involved in debates feel the benefits of argumentation-based education. They believe it has contributed to the development of their skills, which is in line with international surveys. This means that the policy framework supports—and even expects—a wider use of debates and arguments in education (Venkovits & Makay, 2022).

We could not find a single comprehensive study on the state of argumentation education in Hungarian higher education. While one study mentions that debate and argumentation play a much more prominent role in Hungarian higher education than in secondary schools, it is not clear what information this is based on (Deli, 2014).

The CCIV of 2011 Act on National Higher Education states that higher education institutions provide education based on a curriculum. As part of the programme, the curriculum for higher education vocational training, bachelor's and master's programmes is based on the training and outcome requirements published by the Minister. The higher education institution is free to draw up its own training programme for joint training, part-time training and continuing vocational training in the context of programmes funded by the European Union, the Visegrad Fund and the Central European Higher Education Exchange Programme. The curricula must be reviewed every five years. New or revised study and examination requirements may be introduced in an ascending order (Jogtár, 2011).

Based on our non-representative analysis, the teaching of debate and argumentation in Hungarian higher education is rather mixed. In law, social sciences or communication studies, we more often find courses that focus specifically on the techniques of debate and argumentation. This is less the case in other disciplines, such as science or engineering. However, subjects related to argumentation are available as optional courses in most study programmes. For example, at the University of Economics and Business (Budapest), an optional course (Debate and Argumentation Techniques) is available, which aims to familiarise students with the importance of representing their own opinions and positions in a conscious and effective manner, and to teach the techniques of persuading the other side in a cultured manner. They practise methods of representing their views in a credible way, regardless of their emotional commitment. Similarly, at the Faculty of Law and Political Sciences of the Pázmány Péter Catholic University, students can take a course in legal argumentation and legal rhetoric, which aims to familiarise them with the basic concepts of argumentation theory, including the study of legal argumentation.

In 2020, the Talent Management Council of Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE) expanded its range of training courses with communication training. Within this framework, two training sessions in Argumentation Techniques were organised in the spring semester, each lasting five hours. The training sessions were independent of each other, but the curriculum and lesson structure were the same for

both dates. During the training, participants were introduced to the most important argumentation skills, the tools of persuasive argumentation, and their application, which they learned through role-playing exercises in an interactive class.

At the same time, a debating organisation, ELTE Debate, was established at ELTE in 2013. The aim of the organisation was to develop critical thinking and analytical skills through formal debate, to encourage participants to deepen their understanding of current public policy dilemmas, and to improve their argumentation techniques and public speaking skills. The last available information on the existence of ELTE Debate is from 2018 (ELTE, 2018).

The Budapest Debate Union is also an organisation dedicated to British Parliamentary debate, primarily at ELTE and Corvinus universities in Budapest. They organise team debates for students, mainly in English. The two sides must argue for and against a specific thesis (ELTE, 2022).

Law students can attend the International Academy of Human Rights and Debate as a paid summer school at the University of Pécs for €2,500. The summer school focuses on some of the most typical issues of international human rights, including the protection of human rights in armed conflicts, the EU's accession to the European Convention on Human Rights, the relationship between asylum and national security, the human rights implications of artificial intelligence systems, and algorithmic decision-making. The debate course provides students with an introduction to argumentation theory, rhetoric, and practical skill-building exercises in debate and public speaking (Compostela, 2024).

5.3 The Case of Italy

In Italy, argumentation training for young people is almost entirely linked to the debate methodology and occurs across various levels of formal and informal education, from secondary school to university and postgraduate education. In wider generic terms, European values are embedded in youth education through the subject *Educazione Civica* (lower and upper secondary school), specific university subjects and courses, as well as projects and programmes in the informal education system (linked to NGOs and associations).

We identified three main clusters of projects and initiatives related to argumentation training for young people in Italy: debate, democratic participation experiences, and counter-narratives and alternative narrative campaigns.

Debate

The debate methodology is rooted in the philosophical, rhetorical, and Italian legal tradition, where debate is a key instrument for confrontation, dialogue, argumentation, refutation, and persuasion. The use of debate has increased in recent years within the mandatory school system and beyond (lower and upper secondary school, students up to 18 years old), and many networks have emerged to foster competition among students and encourage the development of argumentation skills through gamification.

Below are some examples of projects and initiatives running at a national level:

- [Debate Italia](#)

This is a project of the Ministry of Education, designed to promote the use of debate as a learning method in upper secondary schools (students aged 14–19), through the organisation of national Debate Olympics. All practical activities related to the tournaments are managed by the association [Società Nazionale Debate Italia](#). The first Debate Olympics were held in Rome in November 2017, and participation has grown significantly year after year: in the 2023 edition, 380 teams took part in the competition, from almost every Italian region. Debate Italia focuses not only on students' abilities, but also on teachers and educators, providing them with appropriate training. The teacher becomes a coach, guiding students in the development of their skills.

- [Palestra Botta e Risposta](#)

The *Palestra Botta e Risposta* (“Debate Gymnasium”) project was initiated in 2006 by Adelino Cattani, Professor of Argumentation Theory at the University of Padua (*Università degli Studi di Padova*). It aims to enrich the primary and secondary school curriculum with debate training and the organisation of regulated debate tournaments (targeting children and students up to 18 years old). In these tournaments, following preparatory training, teams from different institutions compete by debating controversial issues, which are judged and awarded by a jury.

- [INDIRE’s idea from Avanguardie Educative “Debate: Argomentare e dibattere”](#)

Avanguardie Educative is a research and action project promoting innovative teaching methods in Italy. The project became a movement in 2014, incorporating the experiences of 22 schools that signed a Manifesto for Innovation. Innovation paths are referred to as “ideas”: they are collected and shared via guidelines, and participating schools can implement them with their students. “Debate: argomentare e dibattere” is one of these ideas, with a specific set of guidelines (Cinganotto, Mosa, Panzavolta et al. 2019) to assist schools in adopting the method. The target group comprises lower and upper secondary school students (aged 11–18).

Democratic participation experiences

Numerous projects aim to empower young people and allow them to experience democratic processes and participation. Examples include:

- [Prime Minister](#) is a free political school for young women (aged 14–19), designed to promote their participation in public and political life and to raise awareness of their potential. It has a national network of schools with physical locations in almost all Italian regions. Topics covered include: women’s leadership, culture and education, civil rights, the environment, Italian Republic and EU institutions, political parties and active citizenship. Each school offers a 10-lesson course, from April to May, for a class of up to 30 young women. Lessons are delivered by experienced female professionals (writers, journalists, activists, diplomats, politicians, parliamentarians, scientists), each concluding with a practical activity encouraging civic engagement. Guided visits are also included.
- [Model European Parliament by MEP Italia](#) is a project initiated nearly twenty years ago by university students, offering secondary school students the opportunity to simulate the European Parliament’s processes. Thanks to a dedicated network, around 3,000 students from 36 schools across 9 Italian regions can annually experience what it means to be a Member of the European Parliament through practical engagement.

Counter narrative campaigns

Populist, discriminatory and hate speech are forms of narrative: stories that describe events, whether real or fictional. These narratives promote particular value systems, helping to spread and reinforce them, while excluding alternative perspectives deemed not “normal” or acceptable (Council of Europe, 2019). Counter-narratives are therefore key to responding to hate and discriminatory speech: they deconstruct harmful narratives and offer alternatives grounded in human rights and democratic values.

«They may do so by providing alternative and accurate information, by using humour and appealing to emotions on the issues involved, and by accounting for different perspectives and views» (Council of Europe, 2019).

Across Europe, counter-narratives have been supported by the Council of Europe's No Hate Speech Movement (which produced a dedicated manual for young people and youth workers), and numerous national initiatives have also emerged.

In Italy, there are several counter-narrative-based projects, each offering features that are worth examining in the context of this report.

These projects typically follow the ADIE model—a methodology used to analyse and respond effectively to hate speech. ADIE stands for:

1. *Assess* the oppressive narrative,
2. *Design* the counter narrative,
3. *Implement* the counter narrative,
4. *Evaluate* the counter narrative.

The process is iterative: meaning that each cycle must be repeated, as no single narrative can fully dismantle an oppressive one. Continuous effort is needed (Council of Europe, 2019).

The ADIE model shapes the structure of Italian projects based on counter-narrative implementation. They all follow research–training–action approach: initially, participants are trained to recognise and analyse oppressive narratives, to understand their topics and assumptions in depth. They are then taught how to build effective counter-narratives, and finally, they put their learning into practice, typically through social media campaigns.

- [Una Task Force per i discorsi d'odio](#) (“A task force to counter hate speech”) is a research–action project by *Amnesty International Italia*. Through **annual calls**, volunteers are selected to participate in training sessions on discrimination and hate speech, preparing them to act as counter-narrative creators on social media and online forums. Volunteers come from various sectors of civil society (students, teachers, journalists, lawyers, photographers, video-makers, etc.), combining their individual skills with the training received. They **work in teams** to maintain an active online presence, responding to discriminatory and anti-democratic comments and messages (Amnesty International Italia, 2019). The importance of engaging in dialogue and not leaving space to haters and populists—even if challenging—is clear, as change is sometimes possible:

“A woman made a comment, and I replied giving her reliable information and a link to Amnesty reports. She thanked me and apologised [for her discriminatory comment]” (Testimony of an activist from the Task Force Hate Speech) (Amnesty International Italia, 2019).

- The Council of Europe's *No Hate Speech Movement* inspired several projects in Italy. One particularly noteworthy initiative due to its features, **gamification and use of peer education** is the [national competition No Hate Speech](#), organised by the Italian Ministry of Education for high school students (aged 14–19). Participants were invited to write articles, create visual artworks or produce TV/radio programmes and videos to raise awareness among their peers about discriminatory and aggressive behaviour, and how to combat it. The best contributions were **awarded** during an official ceremony at the Italian Chamber of Deputies.

Challenges and Opportunities

A common feature across all three clusters is the **collaborative approach**, both nationally and internationally: debates, democratic simulations and counter-narrative campaigns benefit from networks that promote dialogue and engagement beyond the local level. This represents both a challenge and an opportunity: **setting up a multi-level, multi-professional network** that enables real

exchange between stakeholders from different countries or regions (with both bottom-up and top-down involvement: ministries and schools, the State and local associations/NGOs, etc.) may be costly in terms of time, funding and logistics. However, cross-border learning is a valuable asset that enhances the effectiveness and appeal of any project focused on argumentation.

5.4 The Case of Slovenia

As far as we are aware, the concept of argumentation training in the context of youth work (in the field of young people) does not exist in Slovenia or is not widely recognised. However, there are some topics that are related to or cover similar content, including:

- Hate speech and how to combat hate speech
- Development of debating and reasoning skills
- Dialogue among diverse groups
- Active participation
- Advocacy

In the following sections, we will focus on programs in Slovenia that address these topics.

Debate clubs and debate tournaments

Za in Proti – Zavod za kulturo dialoga (Za in proti, 2024), organises debate clubs and tournaments at the national level. These events mainly take place in primary and secondary schools, libraries, student dormitories, faculties, and university residences. Each debate club has a mentor or a club leader. Debate clubs meet regularly, at least once a week, with some meetings several times a week. During these meetings, debaters, under the guidance of their mentor, learn the basics of debate theory, practice various exercises, discuss topics, and prepare for debate tournaments. The Institute organises national competitions for primary and secondary school students, and participants also take part in international events and competitions.

a. Target groups and participants

The participants are primarily primary (7-15) and secondary school students (15-18) who take part in the project through their respective schools. It is considered an extracurricular activity, chosen by students based on their interest in the subject matter. This involves a smaller number of highly motivated children and young people, meaning that not the entire school-aged population receives this knowledge.

b. Methodologies and approaches

Debate is a methodologically structured communication event where opposing sides confront a specific topic to persuade the audience or judges. It is based on a balanced approach, where both sides are given equal opportunities to present their arguments. The methodological framework of the debate defines the number of speakers, the order of speeches, and the roles of each speaker. A structured time limit ensures that all participants have equal conditions (Za in proti, 2024).

A key part of the methodology involves a clearly and simply worded debate proposition, which allows for arguments both in favour and against. Debaters systematically analyse their opponents' arguments, identify flaws in reasoning, and use logical and argumentative techniques to strengthen their positions. In this methodological process, "points of contention" are established, forming the core of the debate, and arguments are built upon using logical analysis and new evidence. As a method, the debate also includes a final phase—analysis of key arguments and questioning of opponents, which leads to a decision made by judges based on clearly defined criteria, primarily argumentation.

c. Differences between debate and argumentation training

Firstly, young participants are "artificially" placed in a position to defend an idea on one side or the other. In argumentation training, we assume that the slogans we are fighting against are inherently negative, whereas in debating activities, both sides are initially considered equal.

The second difference is that the topics in debates are broader. They are not necessarily focused on issues of discrimination, but can cover a wider range of questions, such as mobile phones in schools – yes, or no? Nuclear energy supply – yes, or no?

Campaigns and Programs to Combat Hate Speech

The “**SLOVENIA Speaks**” project, led by Red Cross Slovenia, aimed to raise awareness of hate speech in primary and secondary schools through training sessions for mentors. The main challenge was creating simple, effective exercises to help students respond appropriately to hate speech. Mentors then applied this knowledge through practical exercises, enabling students to identify and address hate speech in their environment. By fostering empathy and self-reflection, the project enhanced students’ ability to recognise and reduce hate speech both in and outside of school. The final product was the ***Handbook for Primary and Secondary Schools: Together Against Hate Speech***, completed in February 2021 (Zagorc, 2021).

In December 2022, the Government Office of the Republic of Slovenia and the Ministry for Digital Transformation launched the campaign “***Ugrizni se v sovražni jezik!***” (Bite your hateful tongue!) to combat online hate speech. The campaign, featuring videos of Slovenian athletes¹, aimed to raise awareness about the rising prevalence of hate speech on social media in Slovenia. The videos are filmed in the form of interviews, where the interviewer speaks to each athlete in a manner that reflects comments typically written online, which the writers would not dare to say to people’s faces. By highlighting the emotional impact of such comments, the campaign sought to foster empathy and promote the rejection of online hate speech. They repeated the campaign under the same slogan in March 2024 but with different visuals², which received a negative response from the professional community, as the content was not communicated correctly (Stražičar, 2024).

a. Target groups and participants

The campaign ***SLOVENIA Speaks*** primarily targeted teachers and mentors of children and young people. The campaign ***Ugrizni se v sovražni jezik!*** was of national significance and, in addition to the public, primarily targeted youth as the main audience.

b. Methodologies and approaches

Social marketing is an approach that applies commercial marketing principles to promote social change and influence behaviours for societal benefit. It focuses on identifying target audiences, understanding their motivations, and designing interventions that encourage positive behaviour changes, such as improving public health or fostering environmental sustainability. By utilising the marketing mix (product, price, place, and promotion), social marketing aims to effectively address social issues and evaluate the impact of its campaigns:

- Differences Between Campaigns and Argumentation Training: These are typically promotional campaigns, which may also be supported by specific educational workshops for young people and youth workers. However, the focus is on campaigns rather than educational events.
- The term "hate" is often not precisely defined in these campaigns, allowing the organiser to present even the views of their political opponent as “hateful”. This opens possibilities for the misuse of the concept of “hate speech” for political purposes.

c. Dialogue and Intercultural dialogue

Intercultural dialogue in Slovenia is understood as a vital and multifaceted process aimed at fostering an open and complex cultural environment. The country aims to foster cooperation among various cultures and promote mutual respect and understanding.

¹ An example of the video: Ministrstvo za digitalno preobrazbo. (2023, January 3). *Barbara Lazovič - kampanja "Ugrizni se v sovražni jezik"* [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/LALHwdvn4Ys?si=crITLpQOCGCxqY2x>

² Bold group. (2024). *Premisli, nato stisni* [Poster]. Ministry for Digital Transformation. <https://n1info.si/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/03/1720007699-sovrazni-govor-plakat-1024x575.jpg>

The emphasis is placed on the active participation of all citizens in the intercultural dialogue, which helps to enrich the common heritage and acknowledges the importance of cultural differences. This aligns with the EU's broader goal of enhancing cultural integration and cooperation.

Društvo za medkulturni dialog (The Intercultural Dialogue Association) is a registered non-governmental organisation founded in 2007 in Ljubljana. Its mission is to promote dialogue on various social issues, regardless of religious affiliation. The society advocates for democracy, human rights, the non-instrumentalisation of religion in politics, equality, and freedom of speech.

Challenges and opportunities

The challenges surrounding argumentation training in Slovenia include:

- **Lack of Recognition:** The concept of argumentation training is not recognised or established within youth work in Slovenia.
- **Limited Participation:** Programs that already exist attract a smaller group of highly motivated students, leaving a significant portion of the school-aged population without exposure to these skills.
- **Political Misuse:** The ambiguity of the term “hate” in campaigns allows for potential misuse of the concept for political agendas, undermining the objective of combating hate speech.
- **Broader Debate Topics:** Debate topics can be broad and not always focused on critical social issues like discrimination.

The opportunities surrounding argumentation training in Slovenia include:

- **Presenting something new:** Since the concept of argumentation training is mostly unknown, the concept offers a fresh methodology/perspective for youth workers and educators.
- **Youth Engagement:** Engaging youth in dialogue and intercultural discussions offers an opportunity to foster understanding and respect among diverse cultural backgrounds.
- **Active Participation in Dialogue:** Promoting active participation can enrich cultural understanding and support the EU's goals of cultural integration.

5.5 The Case of Türkiye

Although Türkiye is still in the process of accession to the European Union, as a member of the Council of Europe, it is a country that has embraced European values. Values such as democracy, human rights, the rule of law, fundamental principles of democracy, human rights, individual freedoms, and respect for diversity have been increasingly emphasised in the education system (MEB, 2024). Argumentation training, which is still developing, is seen in Türkiye as an important instrument for spreading these values to younger generations, and there are various programmes, projects, and initiatives for this purpose.

In the curriculum, argumentation education is not directly included as a subject but is instead incorporated indirectly within certain courses and skill sets, which are mostly left to the preference and competence of the teacher. Argumentation skills are generally covered in the curricula and strategy documents prepared and developed by the Ministry of National Education (MoNE) within the framework of developing critical thinking, expression skills, and communication skills.

In 2005, a radical transformation in primary education in Türkiye was initiated with the introduction of a curriculum based on the constructivist approach and a student-activity-centred methodology within the programme (MEB, 2005). The programme stated that the research-inquiry approach was the most effective method for students to adopt new educational approaches (Köseoğlu, Tümay & Budak, 2008). While the argumentation method was first expressed as Argumentation-Based Science Learning (ABSL5) in Turkish educational literature, in some later academic studies, expressions such as ‘Discussion-Based Teaching Approach’, ‘Scientific Discussion’, and ‘Argumentative Discourse’ were also used (İspir & Yıldız, 2014).

Within the scope of the Turkish Century Education Model (2024), put into practice by the Turkish MoNE as of 2024, it is explained that the aim is to provide students with a number of national, spiritual, and

universal root values and their related sub-values, such as justice, friendship, honesty, self-control, patience, respect, love, responsibility, patriotism, and benevolence, through primary, secondary, and high school curricula.

In Türkiye, argumentation training at the primary education level (grades 1-8) is carried out through various in-class activities within the scope of Turkish Literature and Social Studies courses. Within the framework of the Turkish MoNE Curricula of the Turkish Literature (2019) and Social Studies (2019) lessons, students are encouraged to write an essay on a specific topic, defend or criticise it with logical arguments and evidence, and find evidence to support their arguments. They are also encouraged to discuss historical events or social problems, to develop a critical perspective when analysing a specific historical event or social problem, and to develop arguments by considering different perspectives.

The Turkish MoNE's secondary education level Philosophy Lesson Teaching Programme (2019) for the 10th and 11th grades states that within the framework of the basic philosophy and general aims of the curriculum, it is aimed to encourage students to think, research, discuss, and formulate ideas, to bear human-social, ethical-moral responsibility in their actions, and to show political-aesthetic sensitivity.

In addition, with the 'Social and citizenship-related competencies', which are counted among the competencies aimed to be gained by the students with the course, it is aimed to equip students with social behaviours that enable them to participate effectively and constructively in the differentiated social life as individuals, and to be equipped with the characteristics to resolve conflicts when necessary. It also aims to equip students with knowledge of social and political concepts and structures, to be a part of civilized life that provides democratic and active participation.

In Türkiye, examples of argumentation education in universities can be found, especially in the faculties of law, political science, philosophy, and communication. In the courses in these departments, teachers and students apply methods such as debate, which will develop their critical thinking, expression, and communication skills. In addition, students can develop their oratory and discussion skills under the roof of debate and idea clubs in universities.

However, there are some difficulties and limitations regarding the implementation of argumentation training in Türkiye. For example, no courses or training in argumentation techniques and training programmes have been found in programmes, especially in teacher training faculties. However, there are Philosophy for Children (P4C) trainings, where teachers can experience argumentation techniques and skills, within the scope of in-service training carried out for teachers working within the Turkish MoNE (MEB, 2024).

The implementation of argumentation training in Türkiye faces several challenges and limitations as a result of a variety of factors, including the students, teachers, educational environment, methodology, and curriculum. These include students' lack of self-confidence, sufficient knowledge about the discussion subjects, and group work culture; teachers' inadequate professional skills and experience in implementing, assessing, and evaluating the argumentation method, as well as concerns about curriculum implementation due to time limitations; and challenges in implementation due to overcrowded classrooms in educational settings, particularly in public schools (İspir & Yıldız, 2014).

Besides all this, there are also various platforms, associations, or civil organisations operating in Türkiye to popularise argumentation techniques. For example, the Debate Rhetoric Association, founded in 2018, has signed a protocol with the Turkish Ministry of National Education to provide modern debate training in many provinces of Türkiye. The association takes part in many international competitions, including national debate competitions in Türkiye, with its trainers and trainees.

6. European Values in the National Context

Chapter 6 explores the interpretation and application of key European values within the national contexts of partner countries. By examining how democracy, human rights, tolerance, the rule of law, and solidarity are understood and put into practice in each nation, this chapter aims to identify country-specific challenges and opportunities while comparing them to broader EU interpretations.

The chapter delves into formal policies and laws, as well as the social and cultural interpretations surrounding these core values. It discusses concrete examples of how each value is either upheld or challenged within the partner countries, providing tangible evidence to support the analysis. It also highlights any unique viewpoints that may exist within each partner country, offering valuable insights into the diverse ways in which these values are embraced and interpreted.

Overall Consideration about Slogans, Extremism, and Democracy

When examining populist slogans, it becomes evident that they function by reducing complexity and simultaneously asserting dominance over, or devaluing, another group. These slogans frequently simplify issues to an extreme degree, allowing no room for nuance or ambiguity. Their often-emotional tone impedes differentiated argumentation and discourages sensitive, inclusive discourse. In this way, populist slogans can be understood as fundamentally anti-democratic, as they undermine the open-ended, deliberative nature of democratic engagement.

Democracy, by contrast, inherently embraces uncertainty and self-reflection. It is characterised by the recognition of multiple perspectives, the willingness to accept mistakes, and an ongoing negotiation of dilemmas—features that collectively resist absolutism and binary thinking. Democracy does not impose a singular vision but instead fosters differentiation and openness to future possibilities.

In this sense, democracy is normative—not in allegiance to a specific political ideology or party, whether left- or right-wing, but in its foundational commitment to an open, diverse, and inclusive society built on the principle of equality for all human beings. This normativity is rooted in the framework of human rights, which underpin many contemporary democratic constitutions.

Against this backdrop, an intriguing question arises: can there be pro-democratic slogans that affirm this normative vision? There are indeed instances where slogans express solidarity with marginalised groups and act as vehicles for inclusive democratic values. Notable contemporary examples include **#MeToo**, which calls out gender-based violence, and **#BlackLivesMatter**, which protests against systemic racism, particularly by state institutions. These slogans challenge dominant power structures and advocate on behalf of those subjects to discrimination, functioning as counterweights to extremism and exclusion.

Pro-democratic slogans, therefore, tend to align with the voices of the marginalised and seek to counterbalance oppressive or exclusionary narratives. Rather than reducing complexity, they often aim to increase awareness of systemic inequality and to open up democratic space for underrepresented or vulnerable groups.

Nonetheless, determining whether a specific slogan is pro- or anti-democratic is not always straightforward. Much depends on the context in which a slogan is used, the identity of those employing it, and the strategic objectives underlying its use. In times of social insecurity or polarisation, slogans may be deployed to affirm group identity as a means of resisting marginalisation. However, such identity assertions may, in turn, become exclusionary themselves.

Examples that elicit divergent interpretations depending on one's perspective include debates surrounding gender-inclusive language, the promotion of veganism, and positions on contemporary conflicts and peace processes. In such cases, slogans can either be perceived as ideologically rigid and limiting or as empowering and liberating, depending on one's standpoint and interpretive lens.

While the primary focus of this project is on identifying and addressing anti-democratic slogans, the reflections above underscore the importance of maintaining a critical and self-aware approach. It is essential to avoid self-righteousness or moral superiority when working in this area, and instead to remain open to the complexities inherent in democratic discourse.

6.1 The Case of Germany

Normative values

In Germany, a distinction can be made between normative values, which are primarily derived from the Basic Law but also from religions and other worldviews, and the values that people live by. Both overlap, and both are subject to constant change.

Of the normative values, "human dignity" stands out. A violation of human dignity usually also involves a violation of another fundamental right, and vice versa. Human dignity, and consequently human rights, is therefore a meta-value that is beyond question in Germany and to which every person, including non-Germans, is entitled (cf. Reheis 1999, p. 72). Article 1 of the Basic Law (Grundgesetz GG) reads:

"(1) Human dignity is inviolable. It is the duty of all state authorities to respect and protect it.
(2) The German people therefore recognise inviolable and inalienable human rights as the basis of every human community, of peace and of justice in the world."

There are three types of fundamental rights. Some, like human dignity, apply to all people ("human rights"), while others are intended for citizens ("civil rights"):

Fundamental freedoms: These fundamental rights grant citizens freedoms vis-à-vis the state. They are primarily aimed at state omission and include, for example, freedom of opinion, freedom of information, and freedom of the press in Article 5 of the Basic Law.

Fundamental rights to equality: These fundamental rights grant individuals' equal treatment before the law and protect against discrimination. They include, for example, the principle of equality and equal rights in Article 3 of the Basic Law.

Participation rights: These fundamental rights grant individuals the right to participate in state affairs and include, for example, the right to petition.

In Germany, fundamental rights also include the democratic form of government, the separation of powers, and the sovereignty of the people. In addition to the Basic Law, sources for the value system in Germany include the judgements of the Constitutional Court, the relevant UN conventions, and EU documents, in particular, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention on Human Rights = ECHR). Furthermore, there are values that can be taken from religions and worldviews, such as "love of neighbours" or "animal welfare".

Essentially, it can be said that there is no fixed catalogue of values in Germany, but that people and institutions (such as the federal government, courts, or administrations) pursue a variety of values and legal norms, some of which contradict each other. Human dignity and general human rights are the values that have an overarching effect. Other values, such as tolerance, inclusion, climate protection, work, equality, solidarity, happiness, prosperity, and quality of life, are subject to continuous change (Juraforum 2024).

Values of the population

The attempt to research and map "the values" within the population is just as multi-layered and complex. Age, stage of life, social affiliation, health, income — to name just a few — are factors that determine personal values. In addition, many people are not even aware of their values or state values that they do not actually put into practice in their everyday lives, such as climate protection or solidarity.

The following values have been identified in studies and surveys of the German population:

1. **Family and community:** Family is highly valued in Germany. Most Germans attach great importance to close family ties and see the family as an important social support system.
2. **Education and professional success:** Education is seen as an important factor for personal and social progress. A high level of education and professional success are of great importance to many Germans.

3. **Security and stability:** Political and economic stability, as well as personal security, are important values. Many people value a stable and secure environment, both in their private and public lives.
4. **Freedom and independence:** Individual freedom and independence are core values. This includes freedom of expression, as well as personal fulfilment and self-determination.
5. **Sustainability and environmental protection:** Protecting the environment and acting sustainably are becoming increasingly important. Many Germans attach importance to environmentally friendly practices and the conservation of natural resources.
6. **Solidarity and social commitment:** Solidarity and support for the weak are important aspects of social cohesion. This is reflected in a high willingness to volunteer and donate to social causes.
7. **Health and well-being:** A healthy life and well-being are very important. This includes physical health as well as mental and emotional balance.

In countries such as Italy, Spain, and Greece, family often plays an even greater role than in Germany, and there tends to be less emphasis on career success and economic security. Work ethics can also vary, often favouring a better work-life balance. Religion plays a diminishing role in the lives of many Germans, although ethical and moral values remain important. In many southern and eastern European countries, religion plays a greater role in daily life and has a stronger influence on values and attitudes (Institut für Demoskopie Allensbach 2024, World Values Survey, Eurobarometer 2024).

Relevant populist slogans in Germany

A study has determined which slogans and statements receive a high to very high level of approval in Germany:

- "If you're new somewhere, you should first settle for less.": 65.3%
- "Most long-term unemployed people are not really interested in finding a job.": 50.6% "Most asylum seekers are not persecuted in their home country.": 44,2%
- "There are too many foreigners living in Germany.": 35.0%
- "The many Muslims here sometimes make me feel like a stranger in my own country.": 34.9%
- "It's disgusting when homosexuals kiss in public.": 14.8%
- "Women should focus more on the role of wife and mother again.": 12.1%
- "Most homeless people are work-shy.": 11.7%
- "Whites are rightly leaders in the world.": 10.6%
- "Jews have too much influence in Germany": 8.1%

(Zick, Küpper & Berghan 2019, 70ff.).

In addition, there are other topics that can be identified from various sources (evaluations of publications, statements, election programmes, and corresponding studies and research). The topics of migration/deportation/Islam, political actors, media and press freedom, nationality/tradition, climate protection/credibility of science, and gender are mentioned particularly frequently. It is striking that left-wing positions currently play a significantly subordinate role in the national discourse in Germany. With the entry of the right-wing populist party "Alternative für Deutschland" (AfD) into the parliaments from 2013 and the election of D. Trump as President of the USA in 2016, right-wing populist statements, in particular, have been prominent in the discourse (Decker, Kiess, & Brähler 2016. Decker & Brähler 2022, Hufer 2018, Tiedemann 2018, Kraske, & Laabs 2024, Quent & Virchow 2024). Since then, various academics, constitutional guardians, and politicians from left-wing, liberal, and conservative parties have repeatedly emphasised that the greatest threat to democracy currently comes from the 'right'.

6.2 The Case of Hungary

Democracy, human rights, equality

Hungary's constitution states that "Hungary shall be an independent, democratic rule-of-law state." According to the Fundamental Law of Hungary, "We date the restoration of our country's self-determination, lost on the nineteenth day of March 1944, from the second day of May 1990, when the first freely elected organ of popular representation was formed. We shall consider this date to be the beginning of our country's new democracy and constitutional order." The Fundamental Law of Hungary also asserts: "Everyone shall be equal before the law. Every human being has legal capacity. (2) Hungary shall guarantee fundamental rights to everyone without discrimination on the grounds of race, colour, sex, disability, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth, or any other status. (3) Women and men shall have equal rights. (4) By means of separate measures, Hungary shall help to achieve equality of opportunity and social inclusion. (5) By means of separate measures, Hungary shall protect families, children, women, the elderly and those living with disabilities" (Jogtár, 2011).

Research has shown that democracies in post-communist transitions largely fail to meet liberal expectations (Gallai, 2020). On 26th July 2014, Viktor Orbán (Prime Minister of Hungary) delivered a speech at the 25th Bálványos Summer Free University and Student Camp in Tuzsádfürdő, in which he outlined a new political programme for Hungarian society following the regime change. The speech extended beyond the national framework, presenting a grand vision—contrasting with the ideal of liberal democracy—for the creation of an alternative social order and value system. The building of this new system, according to Orbán's discourse, was necessary due to the changed international order, as the interests of the Hungarian nation and the survival of its existence, according to Orbán, are better ensured by an illiberal social order rather than liberal democracy (Szűcs, 2022).

In recent years, researchers have devoted considerable attention to characterising the illiberal political system that has emerged in Hungary. Analyses have typically focused on the changes in the democratic establishment at the political system level, with much less attention given to whether people's perceptions of democracy have shifted in parallel. In Hungary, both the average and the variance in satisfaction with democracy have increased since 2008; although people are, on average, more satisfied, the polarisation of opinions on democracy has risen substantially in recent years. Compared with European and regional data, the average level of satisfaction with democracy in Hungary is broadly in line with Eastern European averages, but the dispersion of satisfaction is much higher than in either the Eastern or Western European regions. Citizens in Hungary are increasingly divided in their perceptions of the political system. There are social groups who are becoming more satisfied and others who are growing increasingly dissatisfied with the functioning of democracy. By 2018, economic and material aspects, such as prosperity, money, work, and development, had receded from the primary associations of democracy and had been significantly overshadowed. However, this does not mean that Hungarian society disregards economic performance when evaluating satisfaction with democracy. According to a multivariate regression model, a positive perception of economic performance was clearly correlated with satisfaction with democracy. Satisfaction with democracy is also influenced by political preference, in line with partisan polarisation theories: pro-government voters are much more satisfied with democracy than opposition voters (Susánszky et al., 2021).

Rule of law, solidarity

Hungary was subject to Article 7 proceedings within the European Union in 2018, a process that remains ongoing. In December 2022, the European Commission approved all of Hungary's programmes under the Common Provisions Regulation for the period 2021-2027. However, it expressed concerns about the horizontal eligibility criterion related to the Charter of Fundamental Rights, specifically regarding four aspects related to judicial independence in Hungary (European Commission, 2022).

On 13th December 2023, the European Commission adopted two decisions concerning Hungary and the rule of law in the country. One related to the horizontal conditionality on judicial reform in Hungary, while the other pertained to budgetary conditionality. In its communication, the Commission stated: "Following a thorough examination and several exchanges of views with the Hungarian government, the Commission considers that Hungary has taken the measures it has undertaken to take in order to

enable the Commission to conclude that the horizontal condition of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights concerning the independence of the judiciary is fulfilled" (European Commission, 2023).

In her speech on 14th January 2024, the President of the European Commission remarked that Hungary had adopted judicial reforms, many of which were based on the Commission's proposals. Von der Leyen stated that Hungary had limited political influence within the judiciary, as demanded by the Commission. However, twenty billion euros remain frozen, connected to LGBTQ issues and the migration deal, according to the Commission's chief (European Commission, 2024).

Following this speech, the Hungarian government communicated that the European Commission is withholding EU funds from Hungary due to Hungary's child protection law and the detention of migrants from the Middle East and Africa at the border (Magyarország Kormánya, 2024).

It is important to note that the Hungarian government had previously held referendums on both issues. The 2016 referendum in Hungary was a national referendum held on 2nd October 2016, allowing Hungarian citizens with the right to vote to express their opinion on whether the European Union should be allowed to impose the compulsory resettlement of non-Hungarian citizens in Hungary without the consent of Parliament. Over 98% of valid voters (3,362,224 people) answered "no" to the question (Nemzeti Választási Iroda, 2016).

The 2022 referendum in Hungary (commonly referred to as the "child protection referendum" in pro-government media and the "homophobic referendum" in some opposition and non-governmental press) was a national referendum held on 3rd April 2022. The four questions were initiated by the government following years of tension between the conservative Hungarian government and progressive Western European political and civil society organisations. The non-response rate for the four questions on the ballot ranged from 92% to 95%, meaning 3.6-3.7 million people agreed with the government's questions, but an average of 21% of ballots (1.7 million votes) were deemed invalid (Nemzeti Választási Iroda, 2022).

Péter Szijjártó, Hungary's Foreign Minister, stated in December 2023 that, according to international law, if someone is forced to seek refuge, they have the right to stay temporarily in the first safe country, but they do not have the right to pass through multiple safe countries to reach their preferred destination. This principle forms the basis of Hungary's migration policy and its approach to Ukrainian refugees (Magyarország Kormánya, 2023).

After the invasion on 24th February, the subsequent wave of refugees required an immediate response, which was felt most strongly by various humanitarian organisations in settlements along the Hungarian-Ukrainian border—such as Záhony, Beregsurány, Barabás, Lónya, and Tiszabecs—and in Budapest. Among smaller NGOs, the Budapest Bike Maffia and the Menedék - Association for the Support of Migrants are noteworthy. Larger organisations, such as the Catholic Charity, Hungarian Reformed Charity, Hungarian Maltese Charity, Ecumenical Relief Organisation, Baptist Relief Service, and the Hungarian Red Cross, enjoy greater government support and are also members of the Charity Council, which was established in 2000. On 2nd March, the government set up the National Humanitarian Coordination Council, which brings together representatives from these organisations and other sectors (education, health, transport, etc.) essential to the crisis, to ensure proper management. Civil protection, national defence, and the police also deserve mention for their significant role in coordination. Four days after the outbreak of war, the police developed a new IT system to facilitate the registration of refugees, replacing the previous practice of transporting them to various transit points. Public involvement in financial support for crisis management has been vital, particularly for larger humanitarian organisations, although smaller organisations have also benefited from central funding. It is worth mentioning the financial support of EUR 300 million provided by the European Union from the REACT-EU Recovery Fund, which, though intended for economic recovery post-pandemic, is being used to support the refugee situation. In early October, the Interior Ministry announced an additional €21.1 million, although Hungary was no longer eligible for the €100 million funding announced by the European Commission later that month for countries hosting Ukrainian refugees (Tóth, 2023).

The European Commission published its Rule of Law Report for 2024 on 24th July 2024, which assessed the situation across the EU as a whole and in each Member State. For Hungary, the Commission concluded that a series of measures should be taken to meet EU standards on the rule of law. The Panel assessed Member States on four areas, based on the implementation of recommendations from the 2023 report: the functioning of the judiciary, the fight against corruption, media pluralism, and the system of checks and balances. In a separate report on Hungary, these four areas are further elaborated. Concerning the judiciary, the Commission notes that the judicial reforms introduced in 2023 have made progress, such as clarifying when Hungarian courts can refer cases to the Court of Justice of the European Union and increasing the transparency of the Curia's case allocation system. However, the Commission still has concerns about the case allocation system for lower courts. In terms of judicial reform, the powers of the National Council of the Judiciary have been strengthened, balancing the powers of the presidents of the National Office of the Judiciary. In the area of corruption, Hungary has adopted a new anti-corruption strategy for 2024-2025, with plans to pass legislation related to lobbying and the revolving door phenomenon, although there are still issues in this area. Obstacles to the operation of the Integrity Authority and the practical impact of the Anti-Corruption Working Group remain to be fully assessed. On a positive note, the Commission acknowledges that some high-level corruption cases have reached the indictment stage (European Commission, 2024).

Current situation and status of upholding each value

According to the National Core Curriculum, the task of public education is to educate citizenship and democracy. The foundation of a democratic state of law and public life, based on the rule of law, is citizen participation, which strengthens national self-awareness and cohesion, and creates harmony between individual goals and the common good. Active citizenship is characterised by respect for the law, compliance with rules of coexistence, respect for human dignity and human rights, non-violence, and fairness. The National Core Curriculum also aims to foster media awareness, so students become responsible participants in the mediated, global public. They should understand the language of both new and traditional media. Through the development of a critical attitude and activity-centred learning, media awareness education prepares students for the participatory culture of democracy, as well as for the meaningful organisation and conscious shaping of everyday life, influenced by the media. Students will understand the functioning and mechanisms of the media, the mutual relations between media and society, how to distinguish between real and virtual, public and private contact, and the legal and ethical significance of these differences.

Realization in practice

The civics curriculum topics and activities, organically based on acquired historical knowledge at the end of primary and secondary school (8th and 12th grades), provide students with crucial knowledge about the functioning of the state and its institutions, as well as the family and economic roles of the state. The subject helps students become responsible, democratically minded citizens, who understand active and responsible citizenship behaviour. The history curriculum also helps students understand the principles of a democratic state organisation, the rule of law, human rights, and citizenship rights and duties. The film and media studies curriculum for 12th graders aims to develop critical thinking, enabling students to make conscious, value-based choices when engaging with media content and to examine information in the digital space from multiple perspectives (Magyar Közlöny, 2012).

Problems with the Current Civics Education Model

According to the Equilibrium Institute, there are at least five significant problems with the current civic education model: the low number of hours dedicated to the subject, the lack of properly trained teachers, inadequate methodological preparation, the hierarchical and authoritarian functioning of schools, and the lack of institutional and teacher autonomy (Egyensúly Intézet, 2021).

In university education, international studies, political science, communication and media studies, and sociology offer compulsory and optional courses that extensively cover the above concepts.

In 2023, Amnesty International Hungary launched an online course on the Rule of Law in Common Sense. In this 20-minute e-learning module, participants can learn the basics of navigating rule-of-law issues. The course provides insight into the pillars and values of the rule of law and the tools

used by the European Union when legal security is threatened in a Member State (Amnesty International, 2023).

The Hungarian Helsinki Committee and the Society for Freedom Rights, with the support of the European Union, held training in 2023 for domestic civil organisations, including interest representatives and trade unions, on fundamental rights and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. Háttér Társaság developed a "Q-learning" project to reduce discrimination against LGBTQI people in the country. In collaboration with stakeholders and experts, they designed workshops aimed at educating professionals working with affected groups and promoting acceptance of LGBTQI individuals in broader society. The project will run from December 2022 to May 2024 (Magyar Helsinki Bizottság, 2023).

Relevant populist slogans in Hungary

1. ***"Egy vérből valók vagyunk"***

"We are of one blood"

The slogan "We are of one blood" comes from the song *Nélküled* ("Without You") by the Hungarian band *Ismerős Arcok*. The song is often played at national holidays, sports events, and other community gatherings, making it closely associated with social experiences. From time to time, the song has also been used in political discourse, which has increased its popularity. Politicians frequently quote the lyrics, emphasising the importance of national unity. The lyrics strongly convey Hungarian identity and cross-border solidarity. Both Hungarians living in Hungary and in the diaspora, as well as Hungarians in neighbouring countries—who were forced to live outside Hungary's borders due to the 1920 Trianon Peace Treaty—see their common historical and cultural heritage, and their sense of belonging, reflected in the song and its slogan. It is also significant that since 2010, Hungarians living outside Hungary's borders can acquire Hungarian citizenship and the right to vote, thus strengthening cross-border national identity and cohesion, which can serve as an important foundation for building a democratic society.

2. ***"NER lovag"***

"NER knight"

According to Prime Minister Viktor Orbán and his second government, a new social contract was formed in the 2010 parliamentary elections, leading to the establishment of a new system known as the National Cooperation System (NER). The term "NER knight" is typically used by citizens with opposing views to refer to pro-government supporters. This term often portrays political opponents as corrupt, blindly serving power, or as bribed individuals. It is considered a personal attack that undermines democratic political culture and contributes to the polarization of society. Such rhetoric limits political and democratic debate. In a democratic political culture, debates with political opponents should ideally be based on arguments, with personal attacks and derogatory epithets avoided. Unfortunately, the term "NER knight" does not align with this ideal.

3. ***"Hazaáruló dollárbaloldali"***

"Traitorous dollar left"

The term "dollar left" labels an entire political trend and its supporters by associating them with a single negative feature—foreign, primarily American, financing. It often portrays political opponents as corrupt individuals under the control of foreign interests, which constitutes a personal attack and undermines democratic political culture. The term "dollar left" suggests that only one political ideology is correct, with all other ideologies being influenced by foreign powers. This line of thinking restricts political and democratic debate. The term is used to delegitimise political opponents and hinder their participation in political life.

6.3 The Case of Italy

Democracy, civic participation and rule of law

Article 1 of the Italian Constitution states that Italy is a democratic republic. All rights and freedoms related to civic participation are regulated by the Constitution: the right to vote, to be part of political

parties, and to stand for elections (Article 48), the right to gather and demonstrate (Articles 17–18), and the freedom of expression (Article 21).

Nevertheless, civic participation is challenged by widespread abstentionism linked to a pervasive distrust in the political system. This may be connected to several major issues highlighted by the European Commission (European Commission, 2024):

- Law decrees have been used too frequently in the latest legislature. These are temporary acts with the force of law: the Constitution allows their adoption by the government in cases of necessity and urgency (they must be converted into law by both chambers within 60 days of publication), but their use has far exceeded necessity. Their application restricts the political agenda to that of the government, and their approval is often tied to a vote of confidence, with negative effects on the health of the political system.
- Challenges in the governance and funding of public service media (RAI - Radiotelevisione Italiana). RAI is the primary source of information for most Italian citizens, and it has long been linked to political parties. Recent events have shown an increase in political interference from the government, a phenomenon referred to as "TeleMeloni" (named after the Prime Minister).
- Intimidation, violence, and death threats against journalists, including cases of SLAPP (Strategic Lawsuits Against Public Participation): the Mapping Media Freedom platform (Mapping Media Freedom, 2024) recorded 98 incidents in the first seven months of 2024. Regarding SLAPP cases, stakeholders have noted a rise in legal intimidation, including from political figures, as evidenced by monitoring conducted by civil society, which found that abusive lawsuits accounted for 34% of all registered and fact-checked threats to journalists' safety in 2023 (European Commission, 2024).
- Cases of violence against demonstrators by the police, including minors during pro-Palestinian protests, have led to a strong intervention by the President of the Republic (Police violence during Italian demonstrations in support of Gaza sparks controversy, 2024). In general, political dissent and activism are delegitimised in public discourse (Amnesty International, 2024). Italy's civic space is assessed as "narrowed" (CIVICUS Monitor - Tracking Civic Space, 2024).

Despite the distrust in the political system, civic engagement in community life is high, particularly in cases of need and urgency. Notable examples include the solidarity movement activated by ordinary citizens during the 2023 Emilia Romagna floods, and the large-scale movement in Florence supporting the 400 workers from DKN facilities, who were abruptly dismissed in 2021 and relocated to countries with lower wages.

Human rights and equality

Italy has signed the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights and is bound by the European Convention on Human Rights as part of the Council of Europe. Human rights and equality are central to the first articles of the Constitution (Articles 2–3), which outline the fundamental principles of the State. However, several challenges remain:

- Italy still lacks an independent National Human Rights Institution in line with the UN Paris Principles; instead, there is only an Inter-ministerial Committee for Human Rights, which is not independent from individual governments (European Commission, 2024).
- Migrant refoulement in Libya: the Piantedosi Law (L.1/2023) introduced administrative obstacles to humanitarian ships' ability to rescue castaways on their journey to Italy as irregular migrants (SOS Méditerranée, 2023), relying on Libyan coast guard intervention to detain migrants in their facilities. Rescue ships are assigned distant ports as final destinations, complicating their missions. Upon arrival, the crews are detained and fined for not collaborating with Libyan authorities. Far-right parties often criminalise these humanitarian organisations in public discourse.
- The Italian government has reaffirmed its commitment to the Italy-Libya Memorandum, which indirectly externalises the violation of migrants' rights to a non-EU country known for its abusive practices (Amnesty International, 2021).
- Prison overcrowding and violence against detainees (including minors) are significant issues, leading to violations of the right to be free from cruel, inhuman, and degrading treatment

(Article 3 ECHR). In recent years, the number of suicides among detainees has increased. In Italy, torture has been a crime only since 2017, but the Parliamentary Justice Commission is currently discussing whether to amend the law and abolish the crime.

- Remittance centres for the administrative detention of illegal migrants (Centri di Permanenza per i Rimpatri) fail to meet their intended purpose, while detaining migrants without the legal protections afforded to detainees (Tavolo Asilo e Immigrazione, 2024). These centres have been repeatedly condemned by the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) for violating Article 3 of the ECHR (inhuman treatment) (Case of Darboe and Camara vs. Italy, 2022; Case of J.A. and others vs. Italy, 2023).
- Many illegal migrants from the Global South are exploited in the agricultural sector, a phenomenon known as "caporalato" (Romolo Tosiani, 2024).

On the other hand, there are several NGOs and civil society organisations actively fighting to defend human rights, along with Italian courts:

- Humanitarian organisations continue to rescue migrants (albeit at a slower pace), while Italian courts are gradually dismantling the administrative obstacles placed by the government in the application of international Search and Rescue law. The Italian Supreme Court has ruled that Libya cannot be considered a safe harbour for migrants, and that facilitating their interception by the Libyan coast guard is a crime (ANSA, 2024).
- Civil society is active in providing support to migrants through religious (e.g., Caritas) and secular organisations, non-profits, and NGOs such as Amnesty International, Emergency, and Médecins Sans Frontières.
- Civil society organisations and unions have set up groups to assist illegal migrants in their work and daily lives.
- Many NGOs and non-profits are constantly active in safeguarding detainees' rights and raising awareness about the flaws of the current system and its negative effects on society. Among the most important of these are the "Antigone" and "Stefano Cucchi" organisations.

Tolerance and non-discrimination, hate speech

These values are protected by international law (UN Declaration and ECHR) and by the Constitution. The current government is formed by the most xenophobic parties in the Italian political spectrum, and a recent survey (AMREF - IPSOS, 2024) shows that Italians perceive racism and discrimination to be widespread, particularly against African people.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights' survey on the lives of African descendants (EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2023), 40% of respondents in Italy reported experiencing racial discrimination while seeking employment, and 57% faced discrimination in accessing housing during times of economic difficulty. This problem has structural causes, particularly the perception of migrants as a security threat, while Italy lacks adequate state resources to address the challenges of reception and integration.

In this political context, civil society organisations (Mat, Chiodi, & Schmidtke, 2024) (including religious ones) are active in upholding positive values. For example, in 2024, a public school decided to suspend lessons for the end of Ramadan, as many students were Muslim. This decision sparked protests from far-right parties and their supporters but was widely welcomed by the Catholic Church for its open-mindedness (Avenire, 2024).

Regarding LGBTQIA+ rights, Italy is the only Western EU country not to recognise same-sex marriage, likely due to its ties with the Catholic Church (Pew Research Center, 2024). The current government is particularly hostile to queer families; for instance, they have requested that city councils stop registering children of same-sex couples, a move harshly criticised by the European Parliament and a large segment of Italian civil society (Giuffrida, 2023). In 2022, a high percentage of homosexual and bisexual individuals reported experiencing microaggressions and discrimination at work (UNAR-ISTAT, 2023). Although the civic space for LGBT communities is open, discrimination remains prevalent in Italy.

Online hate speech targets women, LGBTQIA+ individuals, migrants, and Roma people (Amnesty International, 2024). At the same time, many parts of civil society have consistently supported these groups through demonstrations. For instance, the 2024 Pride parade in Rome attracted over 1 million participants, with 350,000 in Milan, and demonstrations against gender violence were held nationwide in November 2023 in response to the murder of Giulia Cecchettin, which was classed as femicide.

Social justice, solidarity and inclusion

Article 3 of the Constitution states that all citizens are equal and have equal social dignity, without any difference in gender, race, language, religion, political ideas, or social and personal characteristics. The article further asserts that the Republic (and not only the State, but all social actors) must remove all economic and social obstacles limiting citizens' equality and freedom, because, although individuals are equal before the law, they are not in their daily life in society. In accordance with this article (and in opposition to previous negative trends), many parts of civil society are very active in advocating for social justice, solidarity, and inclusion, often compensating for the State's inability to guarantee equality. For example, in 2022, one-fifth of the Italian population (and one-quarter of foreign workers) was at risk of poverty or social exclusion, a rate higher than the European average (ISTAT, 2023).

Italy has signed the [International Labour Organization's Declaration on Social Justice for Fair Globalisation](#), updated in 2022 to reflect the inclusion of a safe and healthy working environment. Nevertheless, as mentioned earlier, many cases of social injustice persist, such as the disastrous caporalato system, which exploits the labour of both migrants and Italians in a state of need. Once again, civil society attempts to address inequality through specific actions (Italy: eight municipalities published plans to combat labour exploitation in agriculture, 2024).

Current situation of values

Curricular activities in compulsory education: European values are incorporated into a subject called *Educazione Civica* (citizenship education), introduced in 2020 by the Italian Ministry of Education (Ministero dell'Istruzione e del Merito, 2020). As a transversal subject, all teachers can approach *Educazione Civica's* topics during their working hours. Usually, teachers coordinate at the class level to integrate these hours into their lessons, though the workload is not equally distributed. The subject covers three main value groups: the international and national legal system (including human rights and solidarity), sustainable development, and digital citizenship. Each class is expected to dedicate at least 33 hours to *Educazione Civica* activities.

Curricular activities related to participation and democracy are often based on national and European programmes, which provide teachers with educational resources and networking opportunities.

Extracurricular activities in compulsory education: Each school (and sometimes only certain class groups) decides to participate in specific projects led by local or international associations, NGOs, etc. Some of these activities are classified as *PCTO* (Percorsi per le Competenze Trasversali e l'Orientamento), which help students gain transversal competences and an understanding of the world of work to make informed career choices.

Projects are co-funded by the EU under various programmes and directly involve students and young people.

Informal education and activism: Courses, projects, and activities organised by NGOs, local and national associations, research organisations, etc. For example, Amnesty International's Task Forces (Amnesty International) are groups of activists formed by experts, educators, and professionals to respond effectively to specific human rights challenges.

University courses: University faculties such as International Studies, Political Science, Communication, and Sociology offer courses focused on democracy and populism, often adopting a comparative academic approach. Additionally, research institutions offer summer and winter courses aimed at university students and professionals, such as *Populism in the Contemporary World* (ISPI, 2023), a seven-day course organised by the ISPI (Istituto per gli Studi di Politica Internazionale), which specialises in international politics research and education. The course is academically oriented and aims to analyse European populism and its relationship with democracy.

The following are some specific activities designed to promote these values:

Democracy, rule of law and participation

Spendiamoli insieme (Let's Spend It Together) (Parliament Watch Italia, 2022): A project created by the association Parliament Watch Italia to raise awareness and share knowledge of participatory democracy among the public in Sicily, where regional law 5/2014 allows each municipality to directly involve citizens in decisions regarding the allocation of public funds. Recently, the project evolved into *Scriviamola insieme* (Let's Write It Together), aimed at fostering a law amendment led by Sicilian citizens.

Giovani agenti del cambiamento e partecipazione democratica (Youth Agents of Change and Democratic Participation) (Osservatorio Politiche Giovanili, 2022): An ongoing project created by the Fondazione per la Ricerca Economica e Sociale ETS and the Italian Government's Agenzia Italiana per la Gioventù (which administers the Erasmus+ projects for Youth and Sport). It guides secondary school students to study, analyse, and act to reduce the generation gap in their communities by participating in public discourse.

Human rights, equality, social justice

SCUDI - Scuola di Diritti Umani (Cittadinanzattiva, 2024): An EU-funded CERV project led by Cittadinanzattiva and CILD, aiming to contribute to the implementation of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union by training lawyers and human rights activists, developing a legal database and an online platform, and creating a European network of civil society organisations active in sea rescue.

NGOs such as [Amnesty International](#), [Emergency](#), [Medici senza Frontiere](#) have their educational courses for teachers and students, meant to spread awareness and build knowledge about human rights, equality and social justice.

Tolerance and non-discrimination

DiversaMente - Giovani contro le discriminazioni (ICEI): A project led by the NGO ICEI, involving Italian municipalities, civil society organisations, local authorities, and youth centres. It promotes youth-led initiatives to fight stereotypes, prejudice, and discrimination, and to build more inclusive communities and cities.

Social justice, solidarity and inclusion

EPIC UP (European Association for Local Democracy): An ongoing EU-funded project coordinated by ALDA (European Association for Local Democracy), aimed at developing and testing integration strategies for the inclusion of migrants at the local level. It will establish a Community of Practice across six European countries.

Aiutare chi aiuta (Helping Those Who Help) (Caritas): A programme by the Catholic Caritas Italiana and Intesa San Paolo, which, in 2020-2021, focused on combating poverty through food sharing, shelter assistance, and support in job-seeking and entrepreneurship. In 2021 and 2022, the programme aimed to support elderly people and fight youth poverty. In 2023-2024, it focuses on the integration of detainees into society.

Relevant populist slogans in Italy

Populism is a key feature of certain political parties, which is why, in compiling a list of popular populist and anti-democratic slogans, we focused on Italian political parties' communication on social media, particularly among right-wing parties. These parties are the most reliant on such arguments to widen their electoral base (Napoletano, 2023). These slogans have been recorded by scholars and analysts such as Amnesty International in its Hate Barometer (Amnesty International Italia, 2018).

Populist slogans can change quickly. For instance, in recent years, many of them disappeared from public debate due to the conclusion of the COVID-19 pandemic, which removed one of the central issues (pandemic management). As the emergency slowed down, some populist and anti-democratic slogans re-emerged because of ongoing conflicts (immigration, anti-Roma discourses, family issues, and Islamophobia) (Cataldi, 2024), while others adapted to new issues (such as European climate action).

1. Immigration and racism

“Immigration from Africa is an invasion, and it is meant to produce a great replacement of white people with black and brown ones. Italian identity is in danger.”

Given Italy’s location, immigration from the Mediterranean has always been high, and migrants from poorer countries (even from the Balkans in the 1990s) have often been labelled by populists as invaders, a threat to internal security, especially due to the inadequacy of the reception and shelter system (Action Aid and Openpolis, 2024). In recent decades, immigration from African and Muslim countries has been framed as an attempt to replace white “true Christians and Italians” with black or brown people. Italian Prime Minister Giorgia Meloni has also supported this theory (Vohra, 2023).

2. European Climate Action

“Green policies and ideologies are crazy and useless, Europe is against “real people and workers.”

As climate change has become undeniable, people are suffering not only from its consequences but also from adaptation measures perceived as an illogical burden. Changes are difficult and require time and policies capable of addressing the complexity and flaws of the global economic system. Fear and uncertainty have led many to consider sustainability as an unwanted imposition, and Europe as an enemy of ordinary people because of its commitment to climate action (Cotugno, 2024).

3. Sexual orientation and family

“There is only one family, which is the one with a mother and a father. Queer people can’t bring up children nor start a family. They are a threat to traditional families.”

Recent surveys show that the majority of Italians believe that a family is the union of two people, regardless of their gender. However, 37% of people still believe otherwise (IPSOS and Area Studi Legacoop, 2023), preventing queer people from being considered equal. Right-wing parties strongly support this belief (Amnesty International Italia, 2018).

4. Islamophobia

“Muslims are a threat to security. They only want to impose their beliefs on us, to get rid of our Christian symbols, to make us all Muslim and to cancel our women’s rights.”

This slogan is one of the Italian right-wing parties’ prominent narratives about Islam. It resurfaces whenever segments of Italian society (educational institutions, mayors, municipalities, NGOs, etc.) take steps to recognise and address the needs of Muslims (e.g., with mosques or religious celebrations). Recently, it resurfaced when a school decided to close for the end of Ramadan (Il Post, 2024).

5. Anti-Roma discrimination

“Roma people aren’t Italian. They are criminals and burglars; we give them anything they need while Italian people in need are left behind.”

Roma people in Italy number approximately 15,000, many of whom live in Roma camps (Ufficio Nazionale Antidiscriminazioni Razziali - UNAR, 2024), with 6 out of 10 being Italian citizens (Associazione 21 Luglio, 2023). Antiziganism has always been prevalent in Italy and is “constantly and uncritically reproduced, not only in common discourse and the media but also in political and institutional rhetoric and actions” (Pontanfolfo, 2020). This unchallenged discriminatory discourse makes it difficult to address Roma discrimination and their further isolation from the rest of Italian society.

6.4 The Case of Slovenia

A. European Values in national context

Democracy

Slovenia is a parliamentary democratic republic with a proportional electoral system. In Slovenia, power is vested in the people. All adult citizens of the Republic of Slovenia (aged 18 or over) have the right to

vote for representatives of the people in general, multi-party, and free elections. Power is divided into the legislative, executive, and judicial branches. The legislative branch is represented by the parliament, which consists of the National Assembly and the National Council. Executive power is vested in the Government, and judicial power is separate from both the legislative and executive powers (gov.si, 2024).

Civic participation

Civil society is a fundamental pillar of democracy, and in Slovenia, the right to freedom of association is enshrined in the constitution. By providing accessible and high-quality services, civil society organisations in Slovenia play a crucial role in reinforcing democratic values and contributing to social well-being, thus supporting the broader democratic framework.

"The various forms of organisation of civil society include trade unions, humanitarian organisations, chambers of commerce and industry, professional chambers, religious communities, youth organisations, sports and cultural associations, social movements, and civil society initiatives." (gov.si, 2024).

In Slovenia, there are three main forms of NGOs: societies, private institutes, and foundations. Institutes have clear founders. Societies, on the other hand, have "fluid" membership. Foundations are the rarest form of organisation and are primarily designed to raise funds to tackle social problems.

NGOs perform two important functions – they have an advocacy role (drawing attention to specific social, political, environmental, and other issues) and provide services (social affairs, healthcare, family, youth, culture, sports, the environment, etc.).

Human rights

Human rights and fundamental freedoms hold a central place in the Constitution of Slovenia. Their legal protection reflects the country's socio-political situation and the level of democracy and the rule of law.

The second chapter of the Slovenian Constitution, which addresses human rights and fundamental freedoms, is one of the most important, particularly in defining Slovenia as a democratic and lawful state. The Constitution outlines criminal, civil, and administrative protection for these rights, with the Constitutional Court playing a crucial role in this protection system.

The realisation of human rights protection depends on several factors, primarily the political will of the current authorities. The state has an obligation to remedy the consequences of violations of human rights and fundamental freedoms.

In assessing the **permissibility of limiting human rights** and fundamental freedoms for public interest, the Constitutional Court applies a strict proportionality test based on three questions:

- Is the interference necessary for achieving the goal, meaning it cannot be achieved without this specific interference?
- Is the interference suitable for achieving the goal?
- Are the consequences of the interference proportional to the value of the pursued goal or benefits resulting from it?

Equality

In Slovenia, the concept of human rights is grounded in international frameworks, particularly the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights and the European Charter of Human Rights.

Central to Slovenia's values is the principle of **equality**, which is distinguished from equal rights. Equality refers to the absence of any form of discrimination or difference, while equal rights pertain to equal treatment before the law, ensuring fairness in legal and civic processes.

The Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs, and Equal Opportunities, through its **Equal Opportunities Division**, is responsible for promoting equality at the national level. This division coordinates gender equality policy (gov.si, 2024). It proposes, recommends, implements, and facilitates programmes and actions aimed at promoting equality between women and men. Their work

includes drawing up national programmes for equal opportunities, conducting analyses and compiling reports, and raising awareness through campaigns.

The main legal act concerning equality is the **Protection Against Discrimination Act (ZVarD)**³ of 2016, which requires that “all persons be treated equally, particularly with regard to employment, education, labour conditions, social protection and social benefits, education, and access to goods and services that are available to the public” (gov.si, 2024).

This act also established the **Advocate of the Principle of Equality**, an independent and autonomous state body mandated to deal with discrimination. They research discrimination, publish reports and recommendations, supervise anti-discrimination compliance, assist individuals facing discrimination, raise public awareness, monitor the national situation, propose special measures, participate in court cases, and exchange information with the EU.⁴

Tolerance, non-discrimination, hate speech

In Slovenia, the official legal term "hate speech" does not exist. However, this does not mean that the actions referred to by this term are not punishable. The Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia, in Article 63, defines any encouragement of national, racial, religious, or other forms of inequality, as well as inciting national, racial, religious, or other hatred and intolerance, as unconstitutional.

It also prohibits any promotion of violence and war. Various legal acts address this constitutional principle, with the most serious forms of hate speech being penalised under Article 297 of the Criminal Code (KZ-1), titled "Public Incitement to Hatred, Violence, or Intolerance." **Offenders can be sentenced to up to two years in prison.**

Rule of law and social justice

Slovenia is governed by the principles of the rule of law and operates as a social state. The rule of law is based on the supremacy of the Constitution and legislative acts, which form the legal framework of the state. These rules ensure that all actions, by individuals or institutions, are subject to the law, providing limits and controls on the exercise of authority. Independent courts are responsible for interpreting and applying these laws to specific cases.

The rule of law guarantees respect for human rights and freedoms, ensuring that government power is exercised within legal boundaries. Additionally, legal norms regulate the positions and relationships of legal entities, contributing to legal certainty and the orderly functioning of society.

Solidarity

In the socialist past of the country, this word was misused. When democracy was developing in the 1990s, it was not modernised, likely because it evoked associations with the old regime.

Outside political use of the word "solidarity" as a value and related activities are regarded very highly among Slovenians. Many people serve as volunteer firefighters, rescue workers, and cave rescuers. The floods of 2023 demonstrated again that people quickly come to each other's aid, especially when it involves fellow citizens in distress.

According to data from the Firefighters' Association of Slovenia (2024), at the end of 2017, there were 1,299 volunteer firefighting associations and 42 volunteer industrial firefighting associations, organised into 120 fire brigades. These associations included **162,464 volunteer firefighters**, in other words, **nearly one in every 13 Slovenians was a member of a firefighting organisation.**

Both the Red Cross of Slovenia (14,000) and Slovenian Caritas (more than 10,000 in 457 parish organisations) also have a large number of volunteers engaged in their efforts.

Today, the term "solidarity" is often mentioned in connection with the European Union, which provides an international dimension to it.

³ Republic of Slovenia Protection Against Discrimination Act. Link: <https://zagovornik.si/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Pada.pdf>

⁴ Republic of Slovenia: Advocate of the Principle of Equality. Link: <https://zagovornik.si/en/>

Inclusion

When discussing inclusion, we primarily refer to social inclusion concerning different groups of vulnerable people: individuals with various forms of disabilities, people with migrant backgrounds, Roma, young people, children, and the elderly.

There are different programmes aimed at preventing social exclusion and enabling better social inclusion, financed by the government and run by various NGOs or public institutions.

A popular topic in recent years is digital inclusion, which refers to the ability of individuals to access available information and communication infrastructure, as well as digital technologies and services. On the state level, the person responsible for this inclusion is the Sector for Digital Inclusion (under the Ministry for Digital Transformation). They are responsible for implementing the Law on Promoting Digital Inclusion and developing a plan of measures to promote digital inclusion. Their main measure is providing access to training for digital competencies, which encompass the confident, critical, and responsible use of a wide range of technologies for learning, work, and participation in society.

B. Current Situation and Status of Upholding European Values in Slovenia

Democracy

According to Freedom House (2024), Slovenia has a **Freedom score of 96 out of 100 points** (in comparison to other project partner countries, the score for Germany is 93, for Italy it is 90, for Hungary it is 65, and for Türkiye it is 33). According to the national report for 2024, points were lost in the areas of "safeguards against official corruption" (3 out of 4 points), "independent media" (also 3 out of 4 points), "equal treatment of various segments of the population" (also 3 out of 4 points), and "equality of opportunity and freedom from economic exploitation" (also 3 out of 4 points).

According to the Global State of Democracy Initiative, Slovenia "performs in the high range in Representation, Rights, and Participation, and it exhibits mid-range performance in Rule of Law in the Global State of Democracy (GSoD) framework. The country performs in the top 25 per cent globally in almost all factors, except for Electoral Participation" (Global State of Democracy Initiative, 2024).

Despite receiving high scores on various indices, certain areas in Slovenia remain undemocratized, meaning that in these sectors, there is a significant imbalance among different political groups. In some cases, this situation is still linked to the conditions of the former socialist regime.

One such example is media freedom. In the fields of television, press, and partly radio – still the most influential media channels in the country – few new media initiatives have succeeded following the transition to democracy. Similarly, the healthcare system remains undemocratized, with a single state insurance institution (ZZZS) determining what will be financed from the healthcare fund and what will not. A third such area is non-governmental organisations (NGOs), where many key roles are still held by organisations established during the previous regime, making it difficult for new ones to find their place.

Civic Participation

After the peak of civic engagement in the late 1980s, participation slightly declined in the 1990s under the new democratic regime. Slovenia remained for many years the country with the weakest NGO sector (Cepin, Kozoderc and Kronegger, 2014).

The low level of participation was likely due to constant development and economic progress. However, in recent years, growing dissatisfaction among citizens has strengthened awareness of the importance of active social participation.

One phenomenon worth noting in this context is the manipulation of civic participation by political actors. Protests, often labelled as "spontaneous," are frequently organised by stakeholders who are closely connected with political parties.

Human rights

According to Freedom House, Slovenia generally respects political rights and civil liberties. There are still some issues, but they are of a minor scale:

- Roma face poverty, hate speech, social marginalisation, lack of access to early and secondary education, legal housing, and basic utilities.
- Students with disabilities often have difficulty accessing educational services.
- Economic exploitation: There have been some cases of exploitation of foreign/migrant workers, such as withholding payment, etc. Authorities have prosecuted suspected human traffickers.
- The "Erased": Some of the 25,000 citizens affected by the former Yugoslavia, who had not applied for Slovenian citizenship after independence and whose residency documents were deleted by authorities in 1992, have not received compensation.
- LGBT+ discrimination, despite legal protections against discrimination based on sexual orientation.
- Migrant crisis: The UNHCR has lauded Slovenia as "welcoming," but warned that the country was under strain due to the number of refugees and asylum seekers. Asylum centres can be overcrowded.

Education on human rights is also well-established. A notable influence in youth work has been the Compass programme, developed by the Council of Europe, which has shaped educational approaches to human rights.

Equality

The European Institute for Gender Equality (2023) provides the EU and its member states with a Gender Equality Index, which measures gender equality on a scale from 1 to 100. In 2023, Slovenia received a score of 69.4, placing it 12th among EU countries. This score is slightly below the EU average of 70.2. Since 2010, Slovenia's score has improved by 6.7 points, primarily due to progress in the area of power. However, the country's overall ranking has remained stable, as other EU countries have also made advancements in gender equality.

When compared to other project partner countries, Germany has a score of 70.8, Italy 68.2, and Hungary 57.3. There is no available data for Türkiye.

Tolerance, Non-discrimination and Hate Speech

Slovenian courts have begun sentencing internet and social media users to conditional prison terms for spreading hate and intolerance (Cerar, 2021).

1. Prosecutions for Hate Speech

Analysis of the State Prosecutor's Practice in Prosecuting Offenders of Offences Under Article 297 of the Criminal Code (KZ-1) Since 2010 reveals that by the end of 2022, courts had dealt with 491 cases of hate speech handled by the prosecutor's office. Of these, only 34 resulted in convictions, **averaging less than three per year**.

In 369 cases, 75% of the total number of cases, the prosecutor's office dismissed the charges, concluding that the conditions for prosecution were not met. As a result, only 122 cases (25% of all charges) were taken to court. Among these, there were 5 acquittals and 34 convictions (Zavod PIP, 2024).

In 2016, the UN Human Rights Committee expressed concern over the rise of hate speech online in Slovenia. By 2019, the European Commission Against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI) noted that hate speech cases in Slovenia were rarely prosecuted.

2. Reasons for the Low Number of Convictions

According to Zavod PIP (2024), the 2012 amendment to the Criminal Code introduced a condition for prosecuting hate speech: **it must threaten or disturb public order**. This means hate speech is not punishable unless it disrupts order. Before 2012, the criteria for prosecution were stricter.

The Supreme Court ruled in 2019 that if hate speech involves **threats or insults, it does not need to disturb public order to be considered a crime**. This could affect future prosecutions. Despite this,

from 2019 to 2022, there were only 9 convictions for hate speech, with many cases dismissed due to insufficient grounds.

The decline in convictions is linked to the added condition regarding public order. Slovenia is not mandated to impose such a condition based on EU guidelines, which allow member states to decide how to address hate speech. Thus, Slovenia has opted to only penalise hate speech that disrupts public order.

Reporting Hate Speech in Slovenia

Since 1 March 2022, the platform Spletno oko has shifted its focus exclusively to combating child sexual abuse and no longer handles reports of hate speech or cyberbullying. Alleged illegal hate speech can now be reported anonymously to the **police**, either online or in person at the nearest police station.

Additionally, incidents of Christianophobia and vandalism targeting Slovenian Catholics can be reported via this platform: [Report Point for Christianophobia and Vandalism Against Slovenian Catholics](#).

Rule of law and social justice

According to the World Justice Project (2024), Slovenia ranks 27th out of 142 countries in the Rule of Law Index, with an overall score of 0.69, which is above the global average of 0.55 and under the regional average of 0.74.

The European Commission's fifth annual Rule of Law Report for 2024 also shows that Slovenia has made progress in almost all areas: the justice system, the anti-corruption framework, media pluralism and freedom, and other institutional matters related to checks and balances.

At the same time, the Commission notes **a slight increase in court backlogs and the duration of trials in money laundering and corruption cases**. Regarding the expansion of the media regulator's competencies, some challenges remain concerning the resources available and the risks of political influence.

Solidarity and Inclusion

Solidarity is a very fashionable term in the current political climate, but its real impact on citizens remains questionable.

The new **Ministry of Solidarity-Based Future**⁵, established in 2023, is responsible for long-term care (previously under the Ministry of Health), housing policy (previously under the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning), and economic democracy (previously within the Ministry of Economic Development and Technology). As of April 2025, the Ministry had not yet achieved any of the goals it had set for itself.

In 2023, the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia adopted the Law on Intervention Measures to Eliminate the Consequences of Floods and Landslides of August 2023 (ZIUOPZP), which, among other measures, introduces a **compulsory solidarity contribution for 2023 and 2024** and the possibility to organise **Solidarity Working Saturdays**.

The solidarity contribution applies to individuals (whose income does not exceed 35% of the average salary), as well as legal entities (business income and gross income). It is essentially another tax to be paid at the end of the year.

Employers may also organise one **Solidarity Working Saturday** in both 2023 and 2024. The employee's contribution is the amount of their net salary earned on that Solidarity Working Saturday, and the employer's contribution is equal to the employee's contribution (Mercina, 2023).

The corporate sector has responded critically to the mandatory contribution, arguing that it will place an undue burden on already overtaxed businesses (The Slovenian Press Agency [STA], 2024).

Regarding the current discourse in Slovenia, there are no unified slogans or catchphrases, but certain themes and motifs are frequently repeated in conversations. Studies examining hate speech in Slovenia generally do not focus on collecting specific examples, and since the termination of the

⁵ Link: <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/ministries/ministry-of-solidarity-based-future/about-the-ministry/>

Spletno oko (Internet Eye) project, there is no recent information available on reports of hate speech or their content.

Relevant populist slogans in Slovenia

The selection of these slogans relies on the master's thesis of Šegula (2020), which investigated the language and content of hateful comments on online platforms, providing a useful summary of the main themes. Below are some examples:

1. ***"Brezposelni posamezniki družbe ne delajo ničesar koristnega. Mnogi ljudje delajo, da preživijo, brezposelnim pa to ni potrebno."***

"Unemployed individuals contribute nothing useful to society. Many people work to survive, but the unemployed do not need to."

2. ***"Islam širi sovraštvo. Muslimani so teroristi in so zaslužni za povečanje kriminalitete. Pripadniki islama nam dajejo občutek strahu in negotovosti."***

"Islam spreads hatred. Muslims are terrorists and responsible for the increase in crime. Followers of Islam make us feel fear and insecurity."

3. ***"Treba je ukrepati proti priseljencem. Priseljenci predstavljajo nevarnost za domače prebivalstvo."***

"Action must be taken against immigrants. Immigrants pose a threat to the native population."

4. ***"Predstavniki LGBTQ+ nimajo pravice postavljati zahtev za svoje pravice. LGBTQ+ izrabljajo javne finance za svoje namene."***

"LGBTQ+ individuals have no right to make demands for their rights. The LGBTQ+ community misuses public funds for their own purposes."

It is important to note that the statements above have been adapted into neutral and formal language, with the core message and content of the statements remaining intact. In their original form, these statements often included offensive language, insults, and a variety of slang and regional dialect expressions. By "translating" them into more neutral terms, we aim to preserve their essential meaning without the use of vulgarities and colloquialisms that typically characterise the original comments. This approach helps maintain the focus on the substance of the statements rather than the tone or style in which they were originally expressed.

In addition to those already mentioned, hate speech is also directed at other social groups from different backgrounds, such as the Roma, members of non-governmental organisations, members of the Catholic Church, young people, the elderly, and others.

The frequency of these occurrences often depends on which political faction (left or right) is currently in power and the prevailing circumstances. For instance, as of autumn 2024, the issue of the Roma is particularly prominent due to a significant rise in crimes committed by Roma in a region of the country, attributed to unsuccessful integration efforts. Most of this hate speech occurs in online posts, reflecting the widespread presence of stereotypes in public discourse. In the Slovenian language, derogatory and pejorative terms are often used, especially for representatives of minorities or political options/worldviews that differ from those of the speakers. Some specific terms for these groups or individuals include:

Janšist (associated with "fascist, racist"): a member or voter of the Slovenian Democratic Party (a political party in Slovenia, generally associated with centre-right and conservative ideologies).

Komunajzer (from a word for communist): a member or voter of left-wing parties.

Katoliban (a mix of Catholic and Taliban): a derogatory term for a Catholic.

Peder: A derogatory term for a gay man, often used to insult or demean.

Cigani or cigoti: A pejorative term for Roma people, often associated with negative stereotypes.

Rdečkar: A pejorative term for someone associated with leftist ideologies, often implying communist sympathies.

Čefurji or čefurčki: A pejorative term for people from the former Yugoslavia, particularly those from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, and Serbia.

6.5 The Case of Türkiye

A. European Values in national context

The Constitution of the Republic of Türkiye defines the principles of the state as "... a democratic, secular and social state governed by the rule of law, respectful of human rights, loyal to Atatürk's nationalism, in the spirit of social peace, national solidarity and justice." Moreover, Türkiye was among the first countries to adopt the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, enacting it by publication in the *Official Gazette* on 27 May 1949.

Equality before the law is guaranteed by Article 10 of the Constitution, titled *Equality Before the Law*, which states: "Everyone is equal before the law without discrimination on the grounds of language, race, colour, sex, political opinion, philosophical belief, religion, sect and similar reasons." In addition, Article 14, titled *Freedom of Religion and Conscience*, protects individuals' rights to belief and worship (The Grand National Assembly of Türkiye [TBMM], 2024).

At the Copenhagen Summit in 1993, the European Union established the *Copenhagen Criteria* for candidate countries, including Türkiye. These criteria required democracy, the rule of law, respect for human rights, and protection of minorities. Türkiye was granted candidate status in 1999 and subsequently initiated a series of legislative reforms aimed at compliance with the Copenhagen Criteria and the EU acquis (Arsava, 2019).

Between 2001 and 2004, in pursuit of EU membership, Türkiye undertook significant constitutional reforms, starting with amendments to 34 constitutional articles in 2001—27 of which concerned human and minority rights (Örtlek, 2014). These changes included extending the scope of freedom of thought (Article 5), broadening fundamental rights and freedoms (Article 13), preventing abuse of these rights (Article 14), allowing the use of languages other than Turkish in expressions of thought (Article 26), and permitting broadcasts in those languages (Article 28) (Oran, 2001).

Türkiye also revised several domestic laws to better align with EU norms, enacting nine *EU Harmonisation Packages* between 2001 and 2004 (Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2024). Accession negotiations with the EU formally began at the 2005 Luxembourg Summit. However, progress on democratic reforms slowed between 2006 and 2016. The EU criticised Türkiye for democratic backsliding, especially following the declaration of a State of Emergency and the issuance of emergency decrees after the 2016 coup attempt, as well as the adoption of the Presidential Government System in the 2017 constitutional referendum (Economic Development Foundation [İKV], 2024).

In 2021, the Turkish Ministry of Justice launched a *Human Rights Action Plan* aimed at further harmonisation with EU law. It prioritised strengthening human rights protections, promoting freedoms of expression, association and religion, and increasing public and administrative awareness of human rights.

The plan emphasised equality before the law without discrimination based on language, race, colour, sex, political opinion, philosophical belief, religion, sect or similar grounds. It also underlined that delivering public services impartially, fairly, and equally was a cornerstone of administrative conduct. The document stated that values such as social consensus based on diversity, respect for others' rights, and legal equality are not only universal democratic values but essential to sustaining democracy itself.

Despite the continued implementation of the Human Rights Action Plan, the *2023 Türkiye Report* by the Delegation of the European Union to Türkiye noted continued regression in the areas of human rights and fundamental freedoms. The report urged Türkiye to bring its legislation and implementation practices into line with the European Convention on Human Rights and the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (European Union Delegation to Türkiye, 2023).

It concluded that Türkiye had distanced itself from the human rights and freedoms it had committed to as a Council of Europe member. The report highlighted increased restrictions on journalists, writers, lawyers, academics, human rights defenders, and other critical voices, which had significantly curtailed freedom of expression (European Union Delegation to Türkiye, 2023).

According to the *Democracy Index 2022*, Türkiye is the only “hybrid regime” in its region—a classification indicating that democracy is significantly constrained. From a peak score of 5.76 in 2012, Türkiye's score fell to 4.35 in 2022. This decline reflects the increasing authoritarianism of the presidential system (Economist Intelligence, 2023).

Minority rights in Türkiye have long been contested. According to the Conference on Security and Co-operation in Europe (CSCE), minority status requires a group to be numerically small, not dominant, possess citizenship of the country in question, and have a strong sense of minority identity (Taşdemir & Saraçlı, 2007). However, the *Lausanne Peace Treaty*, signed on 4 July 1923, recognised only non-Muslim communities (Greek, Armenian, and Jewish) as minorities in Türkiye. All minorities were considered Turkish nationals, and the treaty guaranteed non-discrimination based on religion, language or race (Turkish History Institution, 2024).

Since the early 20th century, Türkiye has pursued a policy of *Turkification*, a cultural assimilation strategy that does not recognise individuals' rights to ethnic, national, or religious self-identification. Under the current presidential system, discrimination against religious and ethnic minorities has persisted and, in many cases, intensified. Kurds, Armenians, Greeks, Assyrians, and Jews have faced persecution and marginalisation, often being scapegoated in political discourse (Turkish Democracy Project, 2024).

Although Türkiye historically provided refuge to Jewish scientists, artists, and families fleeing the Nazi regime during World War II, contemporary geopolitical tensions—particularly Israel's military actions against Palestinians—have fuelled a rise in antisemitism. Following the outbreak of the conflict between Israel and Palestine on 7 October 2023, antisemitic sentiment in Türkiye reportedly reached its highest levels, driven by widespread public anger over Israel's use of disproportionate force and alleged crimes against civilians (Anadolu Ajansı, 2024).

With the founding of the Republic, Atatürk's reforms granted women the right to vote and stand for election in municipal elections in 1930 and in general elections in 1934—well ahead of many other nations. Although men and women are legally equal, Turkish women continue to face systemic discrimination and numerous social challenges. Key issues include domestic violence and harassment, cultural and societal pressures, limited access to education and employment, workplace bullying, and income inequality (Kadir Has University, 2022).

Violence against women remains a serious concern. According to data from the *We Will Stop Femicide Platform* (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu), 4,099 women were killed by men in Türkiye between 2008 and 2023. The 2023/24 *Global Women, Peace and Security Index* (WPS Index) ranked Türkiye 99th out of 177 countries. Türkiye also ranks lowest in its region in terms of education and social security for women (SES, 2023).

Labour force participation and representation in leadership positions further underscore gender inequality. According to TÜİK's *Women in Statistics 2022* report, only 20.9% of women have completed higher education, 32.8% participate in the labour force, women constitute 17.3% of parliamentary deputies, and only 20.7% hold senior or mid-level management positions (TÜİK, 2022).

The EU's 2023 Türkiye Report criticised the structural obstacles to women's employment, the poor state of women's rights, and Türkiye's withdrawal from the *Istanbul Convention* in March 2021. The report highlighted concerns over gender-based violence, discrimination, and hate speech, noting that the withdrawal was justified by the government on the grounds that the Convention undermined religious conservative values and promoted LGBTQ+ rights (European Union Delegation to Türkiye, 2023).

B. Current Situation and Status of Upholding European Values in Türkiye

The Constitution of the Republic of Türkiye (TBMM, 1982) protects fundamental values such as democracy, human rights, equality, and the rule of law. It provides various guarantees for the protection of these values, particularly the guarantee of human rights and fundamental freedoms.

However, the restrictions on fundamental rights and freedoms that began with the Gezi Park protests in 2013 and spread across Türkiye as a wider social reaction, the state of emergency declared and legal arrangements made following the military coup attempt in 2016, and the issues concerning the separation of powers under the Presidential Government System implemented in 2017, have led to

increasing concerns about the protection of rights and freedoms. As a result, Türkiye has been heavily criticised by the European Union (European Parliament, 2023).

In Türkiye, governments' approaches to civil and social policies and fundamental rights and freedoms tend to vary according to the intellectual orientation and political priorities of those in power. In the early 2000s, within the framework of EU accession and the harmonisation process, Türkiye made significant progress and undertook constitutional reforms on human rights, democracy, and the rule of law (Oran, 2005).

However, the centralised and security-oriented policies adopted in recent years have weakened the protection of these values. Amnesty International's *State of Human Rights in the World* report (2024) underlines the fact that rights such as media freedom, freedom of expression, freedom of assembly, and criticism of the government are restricted by means of repression in Türkiye.

The Turkish education system is structured as four years of primary school, four years of secondary school, and four years of high school. The planning and preparation of curricula at each level are carried out by the Board of Education and Training, operating under the Ministry of National Education. Values such as democracy, human rights, and tolerance are introduced in the fourth grade of primary school through a two-hour weekly class called "Human Rights, Citizenship and Democracy".

This course comprises six units: (1) Being Human, (2) Rights, Freedom and Responsibility, (3) Justice and Equality, (4) Reconciliation, (5) Rules, and (6) Living Together. Initially introduced in 2013 as the "Democracy and Human Rights" course, it has been taught since 2018 under its current title. The course aims not only to provide conceptual knowledge but also to instil core values related to human rights, citizenship, and democracy. Another key objective is to enable students to adopt these values as part of their lifestyle and social culture (MEB, 2018).

The curriculum, developed by the Board of Education and Training (2018), is aligned with values that are considered to strengthen and regulate relationships between individuals, society, and the state. It aims to raise students who respect human rights and freedoms, fulfil their responsibilities towards themselves, others, society and the state, act fairly and equitably, solve problems through conciliation and non-violence, and embrace a culture of coexistence.

Fundamental documents such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and the European Convention on Human Rights are introduced to students. The course also includes national, spiritual, and universal values such as open-mindedness, justice, friendship, equality, sharing, love, family unity, empathy, trust, patience, responsibility, respect, and freedom.

In addition, Turkish, History, and Social Sciences courses at the primary level (Years 1–8), as well as Philosophy and Logic at the secondary level (Years 9–12), incorporate activities such as debates intended to teach universal values, including European values. However, the scope of these activities is limited and often left to the initiative and capabilities of individual teachers.

For example, under the 2019 Primary Education Level Turkish Lesson Curriculum by the Ministry of National Education, it is envisioned that three compulsory and eight optional themes are to be taught at each grade level. Within the theme titled "Rights and Freedoms", students are taught about individual rights, first-generation rights, children's rights, democracy, freedom of religion and conscience, freedom of thought, the right to education, disability rights, equality, freedom of communication, defending one's rights, patient rights, animal rights, freedom of expression, second-generation rights, the right to belief, human rights, personal inviolability, compassion, privacy, freedom of movement, gender justice, gender equality, and the right to life.

Civil society organisations (CSOs) and other civil initiatives play a significant role in defending values such as democracy, human rights, and the rule of law in Türkiye. However, the operational scope of NGOs has narrowed considerably in recent years. Many have struggled to continue their activities due to government pressure, with some forced to shut down. Nevertheless, human rights defenders, women's rights activists, LGBT+ organisations, and other civil society actors continue to actively struggle for the protection of these values (Human Rights Association, 2023).

Despite challenges, European values in Türkiye continue to be defended by citizens, institutions, and various civil initiatives and collaborative efforts. The resilience of civil society, the efforts of academic and intellectual communities, and international pressure mechanisms are critical for protecting and promoting democracy and human rights in the country.

An illustrative example is the “European Values in School” project, supported by the Erasmus+ Lifelong Learning Jean Monnet Programme and implemented by the Teachers Academy Foundation (ÖRAV), established in 2008 to uphold children's right to quality education by supporting teachers' professional and personal development. The project provided a platform for teachers to exchange ideas on how fundamental rights and freedoms, human rights, gender equality, pluralistic democracy, environmental responsibility, and tolerance can be integrated into the education system. It emphasised the importance of both the personal conduct of educators and institutional practices and explored methods for teaching fundamental rights and freedoms in the classroom (ÖRAV, 2024).

Relevant populist slogans in Türkiye

1. ***“Tek millet, tek bayrak, tek vatan, tek devlet.”***

“One nation, one flag, one homeland, one state.”

A slogan of the nationalist movement in Türkiye, frequently used by politicians and government supporters. It promotes a singular Turkish national identity and is often used to justify policies that restrict the rights of ethnic minority groups. The phrase emphasises unity and indivisible national integrity, while also being invoked to suppress dissent in the name of national unity.

2. ***“Çingene'den çoban olmaz, Yahudi'den pehlivan.”***

“A gipsy cannot be a shepherd; a Jew cannot be a wrestler.”

A racist Turkish proverb that denigrates Romani people and Jews, reflecting deep-seated stereotypes. Romani people are portrayed as unreliable and unsuitable for responsible work like shepherding, while Jews are stereotyped as lacking the physical strength for occupations requiring bravery, such as wrestling. This saying reinforces negative ethnic stereotypes and social exclusion.

3. ***“Elinin hamuruyla erkek işine karışma.”***

“Do not interfere in men's work while your hands are doughy.”

A sexist idiom that reflects patriarchal attitudes by confining women to domestic roles, such as bread-making, and excluding them from public or professional domains. It discourages women from participating in matters deemed to be within the male sphere, reinforcing traditional gender divisions.

4. ***“Burası Türkiye!”***

“Here is Türkiye!”

An anonymous expression commonly known among the Turkish people. This expression is a two-way A widely used expression with double meanings, depending on context and speaker. For example, secular individuals may use it to emphasise Türkiye's identity as a secular, democratic republic, while religious conservatives may invoke it to assert traditional and religious values. In both cases, it is often used to marginalise those perceived as deviating from the dominant social norm.

5. ***“İstanbul Sözleşmesi yaşatır.”***

“Istanbul Convention keeps alive.”

A slogan adopted by civil society groups opposing violence against women. It emerged after Türkiye's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention in 2021, a Council of Europe treaty aimed at preventing and combating violence against women. The slogan symbolises the belief that the Convention is vital for protecting women's rights and lives, and that abandoning it represents a serious regression in women's rights.

7. Gaps and Limitations

Chapter 7 investigates the gaps and limitations in promoting key European values through educational initiatives and programmes targeting youth, youth trainers, educators, and schoolteachers within the national context. By identifying these challenges and barriers, this chapter aims to provide recommendations for addressing them in the final report and informing the development of the Stand up For Europe programme. The analysis reveals several obstacles in effectively transmitting European values to youth groups and educators working with young people. These challenges include conflicting cultural and social norms that undermine human rights lessons; a lack of practical guidance for teachers on how to implement values education; short-duration youth trainer workshops that lack ongoing support; and academics struggling to translate their theoretical knowledge on values into practical settings. The chapter highlights the need for further exploration and research in specific areas to bridge the gaps in existing educational initiatives and training programmes. It offers valuable insights and recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of values education within the national context.

7.1 Gaps and Limitations in German Research

Political education and its didactics have been an integral part of educational work in Germany since the end of the Second World War, both in schools and in extracurricular and adult education. Numerous university chairs, institutes, networks and extracurricular educational organisations are dedicated exclusively to this work. Civic education is a compulsory part of the curriculum in all schools and state-funded adult education centres. Due to this abundance and diversity, it is difficult to determine whether there are comparable training programmes to Hufer's argumentation training, or how they are used. It cannot be ruled out that more effective approaches exist. Focusing on this one training model and using it as the basis for this project may therefore appear arbitrary or unjustified. However, Hufer's training is widely used and has been in place for 25 years.

It is also problematic to determine whether there are long-term political effects of such activities. Impact research in this area cannot provide reliable methods or results. Moreover, it is necessary to reflect on the worldview and political stance behind such training. In Germany, representatives of the right-wing populist party strongly criticise the work of democratic political education, as it is perceived as part of the "left-liberal spectrum". The AfD party pursues right-wing populist educational goals through its political education work (via the Erasmus Foundation), for example, on topics such as tradition, national identity, migration, etc. (Schillo, 2019).

In contrast, there is a wealth of analyses, concepts and research on the subject of values, both theoretical and empirical, reflecting the great diversity and complexity of this topic. Even the operationalisation of the term *values* in a research setting is problematic. Does it refer only to deep-seated, often unconscious and contradictory attitudes and convictions? Or to personal life goals or visions for social development? Are these values adopted from others (e.g. from the constitution, religious institutions, the social environment, political parties)? It is also necessary to scrutinise one's own values, which (even unconsciously) form the basis of one's actions – for instance in political education, researching values, or academic writing. In principle, the values of the liberal-democratic order, as laid down in European resolutions, should guide such analyses.

7.2 Gaps and Limitations in Hungarian Research

This analysis presents the results of several studies, all of which suggest that the Hungarian regulatory education system (up to the age of 18, as considered here) provides a sufficient basis for argumentative education and the development of reasoning skills. However, the latest survey reveals that the regulatory system does not offer methodological support to teachers, making it difficult for them to integrate discussions into daily classroom practice. Few practising teachers or those in training know how to implement discussion- and argumentation-based education in everyday teaching (Venkovits & Makay, 2022).

Although this study examines the 13–30 age group, there is no comprehensive research on argumentation training in Hungarian higher education. To gain a more accurate understanding, such research would be justified. Meanwhile, university students can access courses related to argumentation and European values as optional subjects. Additionally, a variety of training courses on European values are available, both free of charge and for a fee.

According to the National Core Curriculum, the subject of civics conveys knowledge, culture and norms, and aims to help students become caring, independent, and responsible democratically minded citizens; value-creating members of small and large communities; and to practise active, responsible civic behaviour. However, according to the Equilibrium Institute, there are at least five key problems with the current model of civics education: a limited number of teaching hours; a lack of properly trained teachers; inadequate methodological preparation; the hierarchical and authoritarian functioning of schools; and a lack of institutional and teacher autonomy.

7.3 Gaps and Limitations in Italian Research

As outlined in previous sections, the Italian education system offers many opportunities to explore and understand European values. The most significant challenge is the wide gap between the availability of information (and training courses) and the time available to teachers: they often lack the time to search for and find precisely what they need, and sometimes the training they undertake is too theoretical. To stay updated, find information, and engage in training, they often work 36 hours per week – twice the number of contractual hours (18) (Orizzonte Scuola, 2023). This highlights the need for concise, practice-oriented educational resources that support teachers in quickly accessing relevant information.

In 2021, UNESCO's survey *Teachers have their say* revealed that teachers in the surveyed countries (including Italy) "feel more confident in teaching cognitive skills, and less confident and knowledgeable about behavioural learning and socio-emotional perspectives" (UNESCO, 2021). There is a clear need for practical and pragmatic training courses to enable teachers to address themes related to global citizenship (including human rights, democracy and other European values) effectively.

Regarding argumentation training, Italy lacks specific programmes and practice, aside from the broader "debate methodology", which tends to cover a wider range of themes and is not necessarily focused on democratic values or discourse. Nonetheless, the widespread popularity of debate methodology indicates that teachers are eager for training in innovative methods based on argumentation, helping students develop essential civic skills.

7.4 Gaps and Limitations in Slovenian Research

No research has been identified that specifically investigates the use of slogans in everyday speech. The studies referenced are primarily concerned with hate speech in written formats, particularly on social media. Most research – and corresponding national-level interventions – targets these digital platforms.

There is a noticeable lack of research on hate speech in everyday, face-to-face conversations. Moreover, recent studies do not sufficiently address societal beliefs or prejudices at the national level. This leaves a gap in understanding how hate speech manifests in daily interactions and how underlying prejudices influence communication.

Challenges regarding promoting European values through education initiatives & programs

Rigidity of the school system: One of the greatest disadvantages of the school system is its rigidity. It fails to adapt to new developments and changing trends in a timely manner. Adaptation, when it occurs, is slow and often comes too late – at least for some student cohorts. Schools also have limited hours available for non-curricular topics – at most, one hour per week.

Over-saturated market: Many existing programmes already address European values – some of them well, others less so. When proposing a new programme, one must "compete" for participants with numerous alternatives.

Lack of awareness of youth work: The youth sector in Slovenia continuously works to promote awareness of youth work among young people, but many are still unaware of the opportunities available to them. Some assume the programmes are not meant for them or believe they involve costs, even when they are free.

Limited reach: Some programmes, such as youth exchanges in secondary schools, only target particularly active or high-achieving students.

Project-based approach: The time-limited nature of projects often results in a lack of continuity or systemic impact. Many solutions remain at the “pilot” level and are not further developed or implemented.

Missing aspects or areas that require further exploration

Our research on good practices and the analysis of existing materials focused mainly on youth work. Insights could have been further enriched by considering materials from other fields, such as social work or lifelong learning.

7.5 Gaps and Limitations in Turkish Research

Research on argumentation education in Türkiye tends to focus on science, mathematics, and language education, while studies on the use or effectiveness of argumentation techniques in social sciences, history, or philosophy remain limited. Many studies employ quantitative methods (e.g. surveys, achievement tests), whereas qualitative research – which could offer deeper insights into classroom interactions, student thinking, and the personal impact of argumentation – is comparatively rare.

Moreover, few studies explore how teachers can be supported in developing argumentation skills, what professional development programmes should include, or teachers’ perceptions of such competencies. In the curricula designed by the Turkish Ministry of National Education, European values and argumentation education are generally limited and appear only in a few courses.

There are also cultural, political and structural challenges to promoting European values through education in Türkiye. The persistence of traditional and conservative norms in some regions, particularly regarding gender equality and freedom of expression, makes it more difficult for young people in these areas to adopt European values compared to those in major cities.

Türkiye’s prolonged EU candidacy status has also eroded public trust in the European Union, contributing to a negative perception of European values. This can make it more difficult for educators to promote these values. Recent social and political polarisation and cultural divisions further complicate efforts to advance values such as democracy, freedom of expression and human rights through education.

There is a need for both theoretical and practice-based research in argumentation education in Türkiye. More interdisciplinary studies are needed, especially those focused on integrating argumentation techniques into teaching, enhancing teacher training, and developing appropriate assessment tools.

In most subject areas, argumentation is regarded as a secondary competence emerging from broader skills such as communication and critical thinking, rather than being treated as a central skill in its own right.

Lastly, the lack of training opportunities and accessible resources to help teachers develop argumentation skills remains a key issue. The number of in-service training and professional development programmes – both public and private – should be increased, along with the availability of relevant, accessible resources.

8. National Insights and Future Directions

Chapter 8 presents the key takeaways from the national report, linking them to the overarching objectives of the project—namely, advancing argumentation training and promoting European values within each national context. By summarising the principal findings, this chapter illustrates how these insights contribute to the broader goals of the initiative. It outlines the next steps and further actions required to implement argumentation training effectively and foster European values based on national realities.

The chapter proposes potential action plans and future phases grounded in these findings, ensuring that the project's objectives are met in a manner tailored to each country's specific challenges and needs. Each key takeaway is connected to its relevance in enhancing argumentation training and promoting European values, demonstrating how national-level insights can guide and inform the project's overall development. By doing so, Chapter 8 lays the foundation for the comparative analysis in Chapter 9, which will synthesise data and case studies from all partner countries to draw broader conclusions. Ultimately, this chapter acts as a bridge between national-level reporting and the final discussion, providing a clear roadmap for future actions and emphasising the significance of national insights in achieving the project's aims.

8.1 Insights from German Report

Klaus-Peter Hufer's Argumentation Training Against antidemocratic slogans is a method that has been widely applied in Germany for over 25 years and continues to be used intensively. This training exists in multiple variations and has evolved over time. Numerous comparable training programmes, guidelines, and manuals now incorporate or are derived from Hufer's model. The target audiences typically include either mixed youth groups in schools and similar institutions or adults who are engaged with and interested in the topic.

Those who actively use populist slogans—particularly individuals displaying "group-focused enmity syndrome" or those identified as "conspiracy theorists"—are unlikely to participate in such training and thus form part of the indirect target group. Whether such individuals can be influenced in their attitudes or behaviours remains questionable. However, some impact may be possible for those who use such slogans unconsciously rather than deliberately. Another key outcome of the training is the empowerment of participants: it can enhance awareness, strengthen liberal-democratic attitudes, and make these values more visible in political and social discourse.

In Germany, roughly one-third of the population embraces liberal-democratic values, one-third is neutral or indifferent, and the remaining third supports more populist—often right-wing—values. Of this latter group, about 10% strongly identify as right-wing populist. In other European countries (e.g. France or Italy), the proportion of populist sentiment is often significantly higher.

As reflected in public approval of populist statements, key themes for argumentation training include migration, religion (especially Islam), unemployment and poverty, homosexuality, gender and gender roles, racism, and, due to historical reasons, anti-Semitism. Depending on contemporary developments, other relevant themes include war and peace, democracy and press freedom, European integration, climate change, public health, and trust in science.

8.2 Insights from Hungarian Report

In Hungary, satisfaction with democracy roughly mirrors the average trends across Eastern Europe. However, the standard deviation is significantly higher, indicating greater divergence among citizens' evaluations of democratic processes. Some social groups are increasingly satisfied, while others grow progressively disillusioned.

By 2018, economic and material considerations—such as prosperity, employment, and development—had become less central to how democracy was understood. Nonetheless, a multivariate regression model suggests that a positive perception of economic performance still correlates strongly with satisfaction with democracy. According to theories of political polarisation, satisfaction with democracy also depends on political allegiance: government supporters are notably more satisfied than opposition voters (Susánszky et al., 2021).

Curriculum regulation in Hungary became three-tiered following the political transition. The highest level is the National Core Curriculum (NCC), first issued in 2012 and last updated in 2020. Hungary has operated a dual curriculum governance model since the transition: centralised and local decision-making co-exist regarding the determination of educational goals, content, and structure. This system applies from Year 1 to Year 12 (typically up to age 18). The second tier is the framework curriculum, which mediates between national and local curricula. The third tier, the local curriculum, is formulated by individual schools in alignment with their pedagogical goals.

In Chapter 1 of the national report, various research studies were reviewed. These studies collectively affirm that Hungary's curriculum framework provides a sufficient basis for teaching argumentative skills and critical reasoning. However, the most recent surveys highlight a critical shortcoming: while the regulatory framework exists, there is little to no methodological support for teachers, meaning that these approaches are seldom integrated into everyday practice. Only a minority of current teachers and trainees are equipped to implement discussion-based or argumentation-based education effectively. Researchers suggest that this gap can be addressed through targeted training and appropriate methodological support (Venkovits & Makay, 2022).

Moreover, the influence of the third tier—the local curriculum—on argumentation education has not yet been studied in depth. Conducting such research would be beneficial. Although the study spans the 13–30 age group, comprehensive research on argumentation training in Hungarian higher education remains lacking, and a more thorough examination is warranted.

Optional university-level courses related to argumentation and European values do exist, and many relevant programmes are available either free of charge or for a fee. The National Core Curriculum is also sufficiently equipped to convey the European values underpinning this project. According to the NCC, the subject of Civics aims to transmit knowledge, cultural values, and social norms, helping students to become compassionate, autonomous, and responsible citizens—individuals capable of contributing meaningfully to both small and large communities, and of actively and responsibly engaging in civic life.

The Equilibrium Institute has raised further concerns regarding civics education. In addition to previously mentioned shortcomings in argumentation training, the Institute notes the inadequacy of instructional time. Currently, Civics is taught only in the 8th and 12th grades, with just one hour allocated per week. This limited provision is insufficient to embed citizenship education effectively throughout students' schooling. The Institute recommends increasing the time allocated to Civics in order to support the consistent development of civic competencies.

Recommendations in summary:

1. There is a lack of recent research on the quality of argumentation training at the third (local) level of Hungarian curriculum regulation. It is recommended that such a study be conducted.
2. No comprehensive research was found on the status of argumentation training in Hungarian higher education. The preparation of a national-level study is advised.
3. Recent surveys indicate that the first two levels of curriculum regulation do not offer sufficient methodological support to teachers. Most current educators and trainees are unfamiliar with applying argumentation-based education in practice. Targeted training and support programmes are therefore recommended at the national level.
4. While the National Core Curriculum is adequate in terms of content, its limited application in only two academic years (8th and 12th grades) and its minimal weekly duration hinder the effective development of citizenship education. A professional dialogue on increasing the subject's presence is recommended.
5. It may be worthwhile to investigate public perceptions of NGOs offering European values training—such as Amnesty International, Háttértársaság, and the Hungarian Civil Liberties Union. These organisations are frequently involved in political controversies, which may affect public trust. There is a risk that participation in such programmes correlates with political preferences, thus exacerbating social polarisation rather than alleviating it.

8.3 Insights from Italy Report

Key takeaways:

- Italy possesses a strong, albeit improvable, legal framework protecting EU values and is bound by international treaties, which render it accountable to both the United Nations and the European Union. When governmental actions contradict these values, judicial institutions in Italy and Europe act as counterbalances.
- Civil society plays an active role in promoting and defending EU values, even when in opposition to governmental policies.
- Nevertheless, the fact that the government is currently led by populist, far-right parties indicates that a significant proportion of Italian citizens adopt a simplified and populist view of reality, particularly discriminating against migrants, minorities, and activist groups.
- As is often the case, populist slogans reflect mismanaged societal fears and challenges; for example, migrant reception policies are frequently inadequate and occasionally contribute to security concerns.

It is therefore of paramount importance to cultivate the ability to recognise the nuances and complexities of individual problems.

The argumentation training projects outlined in this report offer a basis for reflection on features that may be valuable and replicable within the Stand Up for Europe methodology:

International Network of Argumentation

Establishing an effective network among educational centres and schools using a shared methodology—and encouraging active interaction among their young participants (e.g., via international games and awards)—could foster youth engagement and enhance the replicability of the methodology.

Peer Education and Active Involvement of Young People as More Than Mere Beneficiaries

Action research-based courses are particularly valuable as they encourage participants to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts. Equally important is enabling participants to share this knowledge with their peers—through the production of videos, articles, or other creative outputs, thereby reinforcing their competencies and contributing to the project's goal of countering populism.

Gamification and Team-Based Activities

Competition can significantly enhance engagement with complex topics. The inclusion of challenges and rewards boosts motivation and facilitates more effective learning. Structuring participants into teams may further promote collaboration and mutual support.

Regular and Extended Workshop Scheduling

Distributing workshops over a medium to the long-term period allows for deeper reflection and helps participants internalise the concepts, encouraging long-term behavioural change.

Diversity Within Working Teams

Given that the *Stand Up for Europe* target demographic spans ages 13 to 30, it is crucial to form heterogeneous groups. Such diversity can effectively challenge entrenched beliefs and stereotypes that arise from different life experiences.

Preliminary Exploration of Unconscious Biases and Stereotypes

The ability to engage in self-reflection and critical thinking is essential when confronting populist or discriminatory rhetoric. This introspective work can support the development of constructive, evidence-based responses.

8.4 Insights from Slovenia Report

A. Summary of the Key Takeaways from the National Report

European values

The Slovenian understanding of European values is shaped by its distinct historical, cultural, and social context. Certain values—such as solidarity and equality—are deeply embedded, while others are less prominent.

There is currently no systematic or widely implemented education concerning European values. Interpretations are left largely to the individual and often vary according to political affiliation.

Although legislation safeguarding these values exists, inconsistent enforcement remains an issue. Institutions such as the courts, the Anti-Corruption Commission, the Council for the Prevention of Hate Speech, and the Ministry for a Solidarity-Based Future appear to fall short in their efforts to protect these values.

The Presence of Slogans

Undemocratic slogans in Slovenia span the political spectrum and target a wide range of groups, including both longstanding minorities (e.g., the Roma) and newer social identities (e.g., subcultures and migrants).

Educational Programmes Related to Argumentation Training

The concept of "argumentation training" per se is not established in Slovenia. However, related areas—such as hate speech prevention, debating, dialogue, social inclusion, active citizenship, and advocacy—are represented in youth and professional training programmes.

Despite this, a coherent and comprehensive approach to argumentation training has yet to be developed. There is a clear need for ideologically neutral training that fosters dialogue and addresses both rational and emotional aspects of behaviour.

It should also be noted that the training and education sector is highly saturated. Success in this context will depend upon the programme's perceived relevance and quality. "Trendy" topics change rapidly; therefore, successful training must respond effectively to real and immediate needs expressed by educators and youth workers.

B. Contribution to the Project Objectives

Slovenian insights can inform the broader project goals in several ways:

- Narrative materials developed to illustrate violations of European values should be sensitive to national and cultural specificities.
- Methodological inspiration can be drawn from adjacent fields, including hate speech prevention, debating, social inclusion, and advocacy.
- At both partnership and national levels, more structured and inclusive discussions on European values are necessary. Cultural context must be considered to avoid disproportionate influence by any single partner.
- Anti-democratic slogans should be assessed across the ideological spectrum, as they are not limited to minority-related themes.
- Young people and youth workers should be involved in co-creating the training materials, thereby increasing relevance and ownership.
- In an oversaturated training landscape, programmes must meet the actual needs of youth workers, which include not only skills development but also improved working conditions, funding, and long-term job security.

C. Next Steps and Further Actions

Some preliminary recommendations include:

- The integration of diverse case studies into training content.
- The active involvement of young people and youth workers throughout the training design and implementation phases.
- A commitment to addressing the genuine needs of youth workers and learners in the planning and delivery of training programmes.

8.5 Insights from Türkiye Report

Türkiye, as a candidate for EU membership, has accepted the Copenhagen Criteria, which assert that all human beings are equal before the law, regardless of language, race, colour, sex, political opinion, philosophical belief, religion, sect, or similar grounds. These criteria also include democracy, the rule of law, human rights, and respect for and protection of minorities.

While Türkiye initially implemented rapid democratic reforms following its candidacy declaration, recent years have seen significant setbacks. Reports from the European Commission and other international bodies have criticised Türkiye for its regression in democratic standards and human rights protections.

The Human Rights Action Plan, published by the Turkish Ministry of Justice in 2021, outlined commitments to strengthening human rights, enhancing freedoms of expression, association, and religion, and promoting public awareness of these issues.

In 2024, the Ministry of National Education introduced the "Turkish Century Education Model", which aims to embed national, spiritual, and universal core values into the curriculum. However, argumentation education is not explicitly addressed. Instead, it is treated as a component of broader goals, such as developing critical thinking, communication, and expression skills.

Currently, argumentation training in Türkiye is still in a nascent stage. There is potential for growth, especially given the increasing emphasis on critical thinking in educational policy. Nonetheless, several challenges remain.

- The absence of specific courses on argumentation for both students and trainee teachers.
- A lack of accessible, high-quality in-service training and resources for educators.
- Conservative social norms and political pressures that can inhibit open, critical discourse.

Despite these barriers, the use of open-access digital materials and online platforms presents an opportunity for wider dissemination of argumentation training. Mandating courses like philosophy and logic—where argumentation plays a central role—could further support student development in this area. Additionally, the popularity of debate clubs and related activities among younger, more modernised generations may enhance the adoption of argumentation education.

This report offers a comprehensive analysis of the current situation in Türkiye regarding European values and the implementation of argumentation training. It lays the groundwork for developing strategies to empower young people (aged 13–30) to defend these values. Training activities targeting teachers and students alike will strengthen their ability to challenge anti-European and anti-democratic narratives—on topics ranging from climate change denial to democratic backsliding—and foster a more active, values-based citizenship.

9. Conclusions and Discussion: A Comparative Analysis of National Reports

This concluding chapter synthesises the national findings from each partner country, providing a comparative analysis that identifies both shared patterns and key divergences. The analysis supports the core objective of Work Package 2: Exchange and Best Practice, which is to inform the development of a training tool aimed at enhancing the methodological competencies of educators and youth professionals. In doing so, it draws upon national initiatives—particularly those aligned with Klaus-Peter Hufer’s argumentation techniques to counter populist slogans and other forms of anti-democratic rhetoric—to form a cohesive basis for pedagogical advancement.

The findings reveal common challenges and successful practices in fostering argumentation training and values-based education across the participating countries. These insights are instrumental in shaping effective strategies for integrating training tools into diverse national contexts. This chapter further elaborates how the national findings contribute to the broader aims of the Stand Up for Europe project, which seeks to strengthen democratic resilience among young people by promoting critical thinking and inclusive dialogue. The comparative approach underscores the significance of WP2 in informing the development of a flexible, transnational educational framework that empowers youth workers to champion democratic values.

National Contexts and Key Developments

While the national approaches to argumentation training and European values education share some common ground, they also reflect distinct historical, political, and educational traditions.

- Germany has a long-standing tradition of political education (politische Bildung), embedded across schools, youth work, and adult education. It is delivered through both formal curricula and independent, state-funded agencies at federal and regional levels, with a strong emphasis on fostering liberal democratic values as a response to the legacy of National Socialism.
- Italy does not offer systematic argumentation training but integrates related skills through subjects such as philosophy, history, and literature. European and democratic values are addressed through Citizenship and Constitution and Civic Education. A range of national and EU-funded initiatives—particularly those led by NGOs—focus on promoting debate, digital literacy, and combating hate speech among youth.
- Slovenia supports youth engagement through a national programme on active citizenship, with debate clubs and competitions forming key extracurricular activities. The Institute for Political Management was established in 2014 to foster critical thinking and promote democratic participation, but by April 2025 appeared to have become inactive.
- Türkiye incorporates values education through a dedicated national programme, supported by curricular and extracurricular content. The Ministry of National Education leads this effort, often in collaboration with EU-funded projects. While there is a focus on promoting universal and national values, the country grapples with significant societal polarisation.

Civil society plays a more prominent role in values-based education in Italy and Slovenia, while Germany and Türkiye exhibit a more institutionalised integration within formal education. The primary target demographic across all countries is youth aged 13–30, with methodologies ranging from debate clubs and media literacy workshops to active citizenship projects and peer-led initiatives

Shared Challenges and Emerging Opportunities

Despite the diversity of national approaches, several common challenges emerge:

- **Social polarisation**, the spread of **populism**, and **misinformation**, especially through social media.
- Limited **systematic integration** of values education within curricula.
- Insufficient **teacher training** and a lack of practical tools for educators.
- Low prioritisation of democratic education compared to other curricular demands.

- Shrinking civic space in some contexts and **over-reliance on extracurricular programmes**

Nonetheless, important opportunities are also identified:

- Growing recognition of the need to empower youth with democratic and critical competencies.
- Availability of EU funding for transnational cooperation.
- High levels of youth engagement and enthusiasm for participatory and dialogic learning.
- The potential of argumentation training as a non-confrontational method to address contentious issues and foster democratic discourse.

Comparative Reflections on European Values

The analysis examines how European values, particularly democracy, inclusion, rule of law, and solidarity are expressed and upheld across the partner countries, acknowledging both convergences and tensions.

- **Democracy and Equality**

All countries profess a commitment to democratic norms, albeit with differing levels of implementation and political stability. Germany's post-war constitution enshrines democratic values, although rising right-wing populism poses a challenge. Italy's foundational principles are tested by populist discourse. Slovenia contends with political polarisation, and Türkiye's democratic institutions have faced significant strain since the 2016 coup attempt. National slogans—such as Germany's "*Das Grundgesetz ist die beste Verfassung*" (Basic Law is the best constitution) and Türkiye's "*Ne mutlu Türküm diyene*" (How happy is the one who calls themselves a Turk)—illustrate both democratic pride and nationalist currents.

- **Inclusion and Diversity**

While all countries have anti-discrimination laws and human rights protections, social inclusion remains uneven. Germany's *Willkommenskultur* (welcoming culture) has been challenged by xenophobic rhetoric. Italy, despite constitutional guarantees, struggles with discrimination against minorities. Slovenia has made strides in LGBTQ+ rights but continues to face issues with Roma inclusion. Türkiye reflects a complex mosaic of ethnic and religious identities, but minority tensions persist.

- **Rule of Law**

All countries maintain formally independent judicial systems, though challenges vary. Germany's system is robust, though scandals such as Wirecard have tested public trust. Hungary's judicial reforms, while not directly part of this report, are often cited as problematic in the regional context. Italy continues to address systemic corruption, and Slovenia has weathered institutional pressures. In Türkiye, the judiciary has been under political pressure post-2016, contributing to declining trust.

- **Solidarity**

Solidarity is enacted through welfare systems, community networks, and EU cooperation. However, economic crises and migration pressures have strained social cohesion. Euroscepticism is evident in slogans like Italy's "*Prima gli italiani*" (Italians first) or Hungary's "*Brüssel diktál*" (Brussels dictates), highlighting tensions between national sovereignty and European integration.

Gaps, Limitations, and Country-Specific Constraints

Despite evident strengths, the national reports underscore key limitations in promoting European values through education:

- **Conflicting social norms**—particularly in regions with conservative traditions—can hinder the uptake of inclusive values.
- **Teacher preparedness** remains inadequate in all countries. Italian educators cite time constraints and theoretical training, while Turkish educators lack interdisciplinary and practice-oriented resources.

- **Curriculum rigidity** in Slovenia makes it difficult to incorporate non-mandated topics such as values education.
- **Limited research** on argumentation’s pedagogical effectiveness is especially noted in Türkiye, where qualitative studies of classroom dynamics are lacking.

Civil Society and Argumentation Training

Civil society remains a vital force for defending European values, particularly in contexts where governmental commitment is ambiguous. Youth involvement is central to this effort. Germany’s well-established “Argumentation Training against antidemocratic slogans”-model has been a touchstone for 25 years. In contrast, Slovenia and Türkiye lack systematic training approaches, although they engage in related domains such as anti-hate speech initiatives and debating.

Legal frameworks vary in enforcement. While Italy and Türkiye uphold strong legal protections in principle, Slovenia experiences challenges in consistently applying measures in the field of hate speech. The presence of populist sentiment is widespread, with national differences in its prevalence and manifestation.

Recommendations and Future Actions

To build on these findings and enhance the impact of the Stand Up for Europe initiative, the following actions are recommended:

1. **Contextualise training tools** to national realities by considering cultural sensitivities, social structures, and political climates.
2. **Engage youth and educators** in the co-creation of content, utilising real-life case studies and fostering cross-border collaboration between schools and NGOs.
3. **Leverage digital platforms** to ensure wide accessibility, particularly in politically constrained contexts where face-to-face discussions may be limited.
4. **Empower teachers** through accessible, practice-oriented, and interdisciplinary training modules, incorporating behavioural and socio-emotional learning.
5. **Promote informal learning approaches**, such as Philosophy for Children (P4C), Socratic dialogue, and inquiry-based learning as pathways for developing argumentation skills in secondary education.

Further measures include creating platforms for youth voices, facilitating cross-national debates and discussion forums, and initiating academic–civil society partnerships to evaluate and disseminate good practices. Integrating technology and participatory learning methods will also help scale training and enhance its appeal to younger audiences.

By adopting a comprehensive, inclusive, and flexible approach, the Stand Up for Europe project can play a pivotal role in cultivating critical thinkers and engaged citizens across Europe. This comparative analysis underscores the importance of transnational learning and mutual exchange in promoting shared values while respecting national diversity. Ultimately, the project affirms the possibility—and necessity—of a more democratic, cohesive, and resilient European future.

To conclude, it is essential that all proposed techniques, scenarios, and slogans developed within the framework of this project remain inclusive and normatively grounded, avoiding the exclusion or vilification of either far-left or far-right ideologies. The analysis should be anchored in the political centre, promoting democratic dialogue rather than partisan positioning. As a guiding principle, the template’s framing language should strive for balance and neutrality throughout all sections. The tone and content should neither favour the ideological left nor the right, but instead maintain an even-handed and measured approach that reflects the project’s commitment to democratic inclusivity and critical engagement

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11. Annexes: Best Practices and Successful Initiatives

11.1 Best Practices from Germany

Best Practice 1: CounterBUNT

Logo	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online education tool (app)
Title	CounterBUNT
Target group	Young people from 16, all interested parties
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital app, game/simulation • Game/Simulation
Publication date	2019
Partners / Network	Responsible coordination: Niedersächsische Landeszentrale für politische Bildung, supported by numerous experts and specialist organisations. Scientific support: Prof. Dr Klaus-Peter Hufer, Wilhelm Heitmeyer
Level	National (German-language) APP
Description of the method / approach, the theory	The app is based on the concepts of argumentation training to counter populist slogans and group-focused misanthropy. Designed as a game, the app is aimed at young people, who can go through various real-life scenarios and select answers to typical populist slogans. There is also a "mini guide" in short form and a collection of typical slogans.
Purpose / Goal	Low-threshold and playful methods to raise awareness of the topic, increase motivation and learn easy strategies.
Evaluation (result), re-search (if available)	Scientific studies are regularly conducted on the theory of group-focused misanthropy and argumentation training (see Heitmeyer 2024 and the analyses by Hufer)
Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project	The game offers various scenarios and topics that have been intensively developed with the participation of the groups involved and can be used as a model for further development.
Weblink	https://konterbunt.de // App Stores Google / Apple
References, online sources	https://www.bpb.de/lernen/digitale-bildung/werkstatt/293715/konterbunt-app-gegen-stammtischparolen/
Additional remarks	The app can also be used in connection with argumentation training (e.g. preparation or follow-up).

Best Practice 2: Village Talk

Logo	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society activity
Title	Village talk
Target group	Members of a village community
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manual, Guidelines
Publication date	2020
Partners / Network	Federal Agency for Civic Education Cooperation Foundation Bavarian Political Education Network University of Augsburg (scientific support, development) disKurs e.V. (realisation) Various districts and towns/villages (realisation)
Level	Regional
Description of the method / approach, the theory	<p>The 'village talk' concept is a preventative approach that brings together a wide variety of people in protected rural areas in order to prevent the emergence of slogans and derogatory slogans and thus contribute to constructive democracy.</p> <p>In a two-month preparatory phase, around 40 very different "key people" from each village are contacted and interviewed.</p> <p>On this basis, three dialogue evenings are planned, each lasting three hours, which will bring as many and very different villagers as possible into an intensive dialogue.</p> <p>A total of over 50 dialogue facilitators have received further training to support local volunteers as professional process facilitators. Village dialogues are mainly held in southern and eastern Germany</p>
Purpose / Goal	Promote understanding of other values, positions and perspectives as well as acceptance of plurality and diversity, prevention of radicalisation and promotion of democracy, promotion of the village community, appreciation, identification and self-efficacy
Evaluation (result), re-search (if available)	Realisation of a scientific model project, positive feedback from numerous applications in practice
Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project	Integration of argumentation training into a larger concept that takes all positions into account. The focus is not on fighting against regulars' table slogans, but on developing the ability to exchange opinions and look for solutions together in the local area.
Weblink	https://www.dorfgesprach.net/

References, online sources	<p>Wenzel, F., & Boeser, C. (2022). Village dialogue. A contribution to the development of democracy in rural areas. Working aids for self-help and citizens' initiatives No. 53, Verlag Stiftung Mitarbeit.</p> <p>https://padlet.com/FlorianWenzel/hintergrundinformationen-dorfgespr-ch-e3vfuttlv1xl5gvi</p>
Additional remarks	<p>Numerous recent publications in Germany, e.g: Wenzel, F. (2024). Village dialogue. Village renewal in people's minds. Democratic impulses and methodological suggestions. In: Hammer, Veronika (ed.) (2024). Learning democracy. Rural areas and adult education centres Weinheim, pp. 210-222</p>

11.2 Best Practices from Hungary

Best Practice 1: Mathias Corvinus Collegium (MCC) Vitaakadémia

Logo	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth Activity • National/International Project Implementation • Social/Cultural Activity
Title	Mathias Corvinus Collegium (MCC) Vitaakadémia
Target group	Students from upper secondary school (14-19 years old).
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Game/Simulation
Publication date	2019
Partners / Network	<p>MCC's regional network has grown significantly by 2023. MCC was present in 23 locations in the Carpathian Basin - 15 cities in Hungary and 9 cities abroad. MCC opened its first Western European center in Brussels in 2022. The year 2023 began with the start of the second training level of the University Program in rural university centers with a student population of 7,000. In 2023, MCC acquired a 90% ownership share in Vienna's Modul University.</p>
Level	Regional
Description of the method / approach, the theory	<p>In 2019, MCC also launched the Debate Academy as an independent training program to develop and pass on the knowledge and experience accumulated within the walls of the institution. The MCC Debating Clubs were established and operated under the Debating Academy throughout the Carpathian Basin, which has now become a network and welcomes those who wish to debate in eight centers. It provides individual mentoring assistance to the best debaters, conducts competition preparations in English for the Debate Academy's own British Parliamentary debate team and participates in international debate competitions. In addition, it provides uniform, high-quality logic education for all participants of the Junior program. In addition to skill-building training, education</p>

	and mentoring, continuous professional workshops take place within the walls of the Debate Academy: follow-up of the latest scientific trends and methodology, curriculum development, writing manuals for debate leaders. The Polemia blog of the Corvinák website features analytical essays related to the world of debating, and the Polemia podcast promotes rational debate through various talk and debate programs.
Purpose / Goal	During its more than 25-year career, MCC has always paid special attention to the formation and development of the basic skills of logic, reasoning and rhetoric, as well as the ability to debate in all programs of its complex training range. Rational debate as a method serves as an essential tool in MCC's two main endeavors: talent nurturing and community building.
Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking • Development of communication and argumentation skills • Language learning • Talent management • Community building • Preparation for competition • Improvisation
Weblink	https://vitaakademia.mcc.hu/kepzesek
References, online sources	https://real.mtak.hu/72830/1/genezys_02.pdf https://vitaakademia.mcc.hu/index.php/vitaklub-halozat

Best Practice 2: Eltevita

Logo	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth Activity • Lesson Plan/Activity • National/International Project Implementation • Social/Cultural Activity
Title	Elte vitaklub
Target group	University students
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Game/Simulation
Publication date	2013
Partners / Network	Central European University (CEU), Budapesti Corvinus Egyetem, Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem
Level	International
Description of the method / approach, the theory	The Elte debate is modeled on the British parliamentary debate, but at the same time trainings and public debates are also organized. During the public debate, a group discussion is built on the presentation of an invited specialist. The ELTE Debate Club together with the Corvinus Debate Club organized speech

	and debate skills development training for university students and high school graduates.
Purpose / Goal	The purpose of the Elte debate is to increase the level of dialogue, to develop the debate culture and communication skills of university students. The purpose of the ELTE debate is also to develop students' critical thinking and to shed light on social problems.
Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking • Development of communication and argumentation skills • Language learning • Talent management • Community building • Preparation for competition • Improvisation • Exploring social problems, broadening horizons
Weblink	https://www.elte.hu/content/tanulj-vitazni.e.12090 https://alumni.uni-corvinus.hu/topics/32825/feed

11.3 Best Practices from Italy

Best Practice 1: Debate Italia

Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth Activity • National/International Project Implementation • School Activity
Title	Debate Italia
Target group	Students from upper secondary school (14-19 years old) and teachers.
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Game/Simulation
Publication date	The first Debate Olympics were held in Rome in November 2017. The project is ongoing.
Partners / Network	<p>Debate Italia is a project of the Ministry of Education</p> <p>Società Nazionale Debate Italia (SN-DI) manages and coordinates the activities</p> <p>The WeDebate network counts 270 Italian secondary schools</p>
Level	National and International/EU
Description of the method / approach, the theory	The national championships are governed by a set of rules that takes as its reference the debate model practiced at the World Schools Debating Championships and includes prepared and

	<p>impromptu topics, based on improvisation. A debate requires a team that agrees with the assumption under discussion (pro) and another team that doesn't agree (against). Before starting the debate, each team communicates to the judge the names of the 3 speakers who will speak and their order. During the discussion, speakers from both teams alternate. The team against the assumption is entitled to make a question to the opponents. Speakers can communicate only with each other. A timekeeper keeps track of the speech length: they can last 8 minutes, while the final one is only 4 minutes. When the debate is over, the judge decides which team is the winner, based on contents, style and communication strategy. All topics are decided by a specific committee, and they can deal with a variety of subjects. SN-DI shared a set of resources to train teachers, which were the results of DEUS - Dealing with Euroscepticism, a EU-funded project they took part in as partners. The Guide for Depolarisation for Debate Coaches is a set of exercises for educators to use the debate methodology. It is proposed to be used with the research paper The Polarised Landscape in Europe, an analysis of the concepts at the basis of the European Union.</p>
<p>Purpose / Goal</p>	<p>The purpose is to provide students with techniques and strategies to manage a debate and develop argumentation skills to communicate effectively, to know how to speak in public and defend their own opinions, to know how to respond to accusations or the other side based on valuable research. At the end of the project participants will gain awareness of the responsibilities, rights and duties involved in being a member of a community, pay attention and respect each other's point of view, critically evaluate information; recognize the values of Citizenship and the Constitution.</p>
<p>Evaluation (result), re-search (if available)</p>	<p>The debate is a mental sport capable of fostering awareness and participation, providing students with tools to independently understand reality and society. It also encourages teamwork. Developing interest in issues that affect society enables young people to take an active role in decision-making processes. Debating issues related to political, social, economic, scientific and cultural current events makes students grow, as they grasp the most concrete aspects of reality, beyond any easy populism. Teachers can consolidate more engaging and dynamic teaching methods.</p>
<p>Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project</p>	<p>The following insights can be drawn from the Debate Italia experience that can contribute to the effectiveness of argumentative practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the process and preparation steps; having a regulation, a clear structure and rules ● training in communication, public speaking and listening ● gamification; introducing healthy competition ● use of prepared and impromptu topics, based on improvisation ● propose different themes; one for the Italian competition and one in English for the international competition

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> refer to an international network; relations with other European countries
Weblink	www.debateitalia.it
References, online sources	Debate Italia, Regolamento, www.debateitalia.it

Best Practice 2: REACT – No Hate

Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice	<p>Respect and Equality: Acting and Communicating Together</p>
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School subject Youth Activity Lesson Plan/Activity Online Education Resource Activity Civil Society Activity National/International Project Implementation Social/Cultural Activity
Title	REACT – No Hate
Target group	Students from 14 to 18 years old
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curriculum/ Course/Lesson plan/Learning activity Toolkit Digital Device (e.g., mobile)/ Online Tool(s), Application(s), LMS or Platform Game/Simulation Report, Handbook/ Guidelines Assessment (type e.g., self-, peer-assessment) process
Partners / Network	<p>List of the partners/organization/institution involved, if applicable</p> <p>a) Name of the partner b) Country of origin c) Role in the practice</p>
Description of the method / approach, the theory	<p><u><i>React - Respect and Equality: Acting and Communicating Together</i></u> is a project co-financed by the EU as part of the program “Rights, Equality and Citizenship” and it brings together partners from Italy, Spain, Germany France and UK to create resources to counter online hate speech. During the project, students from 14 to 18 were trained in 5 or 6 two-hour workshops in class over a period of about two months. In this way, participants had the chance to reflect, discuss and elaborate the work done, while exploring and further deepening their knowledge about the topics involved.</p> <p><i>Meetings were organised in two phases: the first was dedicated to reflecting on the possible consequences of prejudices and violent or aggressive online messages; the second was devoted to constructing a counter-narrative campaign together.</i></p> <p>In the project’s Educational Toolkit, a set of exercises for countering stereotypes is provided: activities meant to reflect on the stereotypes and prejudices we aren’t aware of replicating and to understand their impact on our and others’ lives.</p> <p>The strategy outlined to reach the objectives is based on a horizontal and multidisciplinary approach and on target groups</p>

	<p>active participation. It will be implemented through the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. systematic quantitative and qualitative monitoring of hate speech and recording of counter narratives effective examples throughout a selection of online media, including social media, in Italy, UK, France, Germany and Spain: recording through an ad hoc ICT tool, qualitative analysis and reporting; 2. mutual learning and exchange of best practices among key actors – teachers, youth operators, representatives of the targeted communities, researchers, policy-makers, social media platforms representatives, online press representatives and CSOs – on positive actions to foster tolerance, counter hate speech and on means and mechanisms to facilitate reporting and enhancing transparency of counter-speech; 3. capacity building and training activities focusing on media literacy both addressed to teachers and youth workers and directly to young people. Particular attention will be given in addressing the capacity building and training activities to different categories of youngsters, including with minority background. Workshops will adopt a highly participatory approach; in particular youngsters will be actively involved in the construction of a solid counter-narrative. The communication tools elaborated by the youngsters will be then spread; 4. dissemination and awareness raising campaign based on the use of the tools realised by the youngsters that will be presented at local level and spread thoroughly on social media and the Internet.
<p>Purpose / Goal</p>	<p>In order to contribute to monitoring and counter online hate speech based on (and determining) anti-Muslim intolerance and hatred, the proposed project aimed at collecting qualitative and quantitative evidences of online hate speech and of counter narratives effective examples; identify positive actions to foster tolerance, counter hate speech, facilitate reporting and enhance transparency of counter-speech and share it among key actors, promoting media literacy and spreading counter-narrative among youngsters.</p>
<p>Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Workshops' frequency <p>Spreading the workshops over a medium/long period of time might encourage reflection and help to develop a habit.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preliminary study on one's own discriminatory and stereotypical beliefs (especially those of which we are unaware) <p>Being capable of self-doubt and critical thinking is important when dealing with populist and discriminatory speeches, in order to find the best ways to respond and react in a constructive way.</p>
<p>Weblink</p>	<p>http://www.reactnohate.eu</p>

11.4 Best Practices from Slovenia

Best Practice 1: “Dates” of political opposites

<p>Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice</p>	
<p>Topic / Area</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth Activity • Online Education Resource Activity • International Project Implementation
<p>Title</p>	<p>“Dates” of political opposites</p>
<p>Target group</p>	<p>Teachers and youth workers Young people (15-30) It can be used also in adult education</p>
<p>Type</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning activity • Application
<p>Date released</p>	<p>March 2024</p>
<p>Partners / Network</p>	<p>Socialna akademija, Slovenia (leading partner) Documenta, Croatia KatHaz, Hungary InicativAngola, Austria</p>
<p>Level</p>	<p>International/EU project partnership</p>
<p>Description of the method / approach, the theory</p>	<p>HardTopics.eu is a web application designed to help youth workers to facilitate dialogue between individuals who hold opposing views on a particular topic.</p> <p>In a dialogical event, called “dates of political opponents”, participants are paired according to previously expressed opinions. The opinion pool is created by youth workers. The goal of the algorithm is that couples are made of people with the most opposing opinions.</p> <p>After being paired, couples engage in a conversation where they discuss the issues, seek common ground, and learn to accept differing perspectives.</p> <p>The application is suitable for use in groups of young people (as well as other age groups), typically ranging from 10 to 40 participants (it can accommodate larger numbers as well), being together in one space or remote.</p> <p>It is utilized as part of structured activities, during which participants not only engage with the application but also take part in discussions that outline key guidelines for productive dialogue.</p> <p>These discussions emphasize the importance of adhering to rules of respectful communication and creating an environment conducive to meaningful, open exchange of ideas.</p>

<p>Purpose / Goal</p>	<p>The purpose of this app is to foster constructive dialogue between individuals with opposing viewpoints and to work against social polarization.</p> <p>By bringing people together in a moderate, structured environment, the app encourages respectful conversation, mutual understanding, and the identification of common ground.</p> <p>It is designed to help participants develop skills in critical thinking, empathy, and the ability to engage in civil discourse, especially on contentious topics. The goal is to bridge divides and promote a culture of tolerance and acceptance of diverse opinions.</p>
<p>Evaluation (result), re-search (if available)</p>	<p>The app has proven to be highly effective across a range of group settings, including schools, youth organizations, both coherent and mixed groups, as well as international youth exchanges.</p> <p>In each instance, it has consistently yielded positive outcomes, fostered meaningful dialogue and understood among participants. Its versatility in adapting to diverse audiences underscores its value as a tool for facilitating constructive conversations and promoting mutual respect in various contexts.</p>
<p>Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project</p>	<p>This app is particularly valuable for projects that focus on fostering dialogue with individuals who hold opposing views—people whom participants might typically avoid engaging with.</p> <p>By providing a moderate environment, the app goes beyond simple debate, enabling genuine dialogue.</p> <p>It allows for deeper understanding, mutual respect, and the exploration of differing perspectives, making it an effective tool for breaking down barriers and encouraging open communication between people with fundamentally different viewpoints.</p>
<p>Weblink</p>	<p>https://hardtopics.eu/</p>
<p>References/ online sources</p>	<p>Application: https://hardtopics.eu/ (in Slovenian, English, German, Croatian and Hungarian) About the project: https://socialna-akademija.si/tezke-teme/ Training of youth workers in Szeged: https://socialna-akademija.si/za-mladinske-delavce-tezke-teme-szeged-18-22-3-2024/ Example of an event, at which the app was used: https://socialna-akademija.si/navdusujoca-izkusnja-na-dogodku-evropske-dileme-v-okviru-evropskega-tedna-mladih/</p>

Best Practice 2: Outside In – Transforming Hate

<p>Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice</p>	
<p>Topic / Area</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lesson Plan/Activity • Online Education Resource Activity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National/International Project Implementation
Title	Outside In – Transforming Hate
Target group	Youth workers engage with young people who express hateful speech and/or behaviour in youth settings.
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curriculum/ Course/Lesson plan/Learning activity Handbook/ Guidelines
Date released	December 2018
Partners / Network	<p>National Youth Council of Ireland, Ireland</p> <p>Ljubljana Pride, Slovenia</p> <p>Interfaith Scotland, United Kingdom</p> <p>Ha Moment, Portugal</p> <p>Rauhankasvatus Instituutti, Finland</p>
Level	International/EU level
Description of the method / approach, the theory	<p>"Outside In – Transforming Hate" was a two-year project (2017-2018) aimed at making youth work in Europe more inclusive.</p> <p>Five partner organizations from Finland, Ireland, Portugal, Scotland, and Slovenia co-created a European network of trainers and experts to help youth workers recognize, manage, and transform hateful speech and behaviour.</p> <p>What makes this project unique is that the trainers were youth workers and equality experts from minority and marginalized groups. They underwent an intensive training-of-trainers program and co-created a practice manual for inclusive youth work.</p> <p>The process of addressing hateful behaviours addresses these phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognizing hate, tackling hate, transforming hate. <p>It suggests both measures that can be applied on interpersonal as well as on organizational level.</p>
Purpose / Goal	<p>The aim of the project was to make youth work in Europe more inclusive by equipping youth workers with the skills and tools to recognize, manage, and transform hateful speech and behaviour.</p> <p>Through collaboration among five partner countries, the project created a network of trainers from marginalized groups, offering training and resources to foster safer spaces and long-term change among youth with discriminatory attitudes.</p>
Evaluation (result), re-search (if available)	<p>The "Outside In" project resulted in the creation of a practice manual for youth workers, designed to address hateful speech and behaviour in youth settings. The manual includes chapters on understanding youth work, recognizing and transforming hate, and practical methodologies applicable in both formal and non-formal settings. A Practical Tool Kit offers resources for</p>

	<p>youth workers, making this a flexible guide for transforming challenging behavior and promoting inclusive environments.</p> <p>In 2018, around 500 people, active in youth work, were trained through the project.</p>
Overview of the relevant aspects that are important for this project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It provides youth workers with tools, methods, and approaches to recognize, manage, and constructively address hateful speech and behavior. • Addresses are different types of discrimination. • Works on situations: before the hate speech happens, in the moment as it happens and after it has already happened. • Methodologies in the manual can be applied in various settings to encourage long-term change in discriminatory attitudes – but are specialized into youth work.
Web link	https://transforminghate.net/
References/ online sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website: https://transforminghate.net/ • Manual (digital): https://transforminghate.net/toolsandpractise/ • Manual (PDF): https://transforminghate.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/outside-in-manual-full.pdf

11.5 Best Practices from Türkiye

Best Practice 1: Demokleos Project (EU Erasmus+)

Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice	
Topic / Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission Erasmus+ KA201 Strategic Partnerships for School Education Program
Title	<p>DEMOKLEOS (Rethinking Democratic Awareness and Collective Responsibility for a Whole-School Approach)</p> <p>Ref. No: 2015-1-EL01-KA201-013930</p>
Target group	<p>DEMOKLEOS focuses on "target groups" in the field of education - mainly young people. The aim is to inspire them to actively contribute to European integration in the context of increasing intercultural and religious diversity.</p> <p>Another important target group is all educators and teachers in their role as facilitators. Teachers and researchers have worked together on the research, development and implementation of joint organisations' educational tools and resources to achieve this goal.</p>
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curriculum/ Course/Lesson plan/Learning activity • Report

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handbook/ Guidelines
Date released	Project Starting date: 01/09/2015 Project Ending date: 31/08/2018
Partners / Network	<p>Directorate of Secondary Education of Piraeus (Greece, Coordinator)</p> <p>Learning For Integration RY (Finland)</p> <p>Ionidios Model Experimental Lyceum (Greece)</p> <p>9th Gymnasium of Piraeus (Greece)</p> <p>1st EPAL of Piraeus (Greece)</p> <p>University of Piraeus Research Center (Greece)</p> <p>European University of Cyprus (Cyprus)</p> <p>Doğa Schools (Türkiye)</p> <p>Agrupamento De Escolas De Pombal (Portugal)</p> <p>University of Leibniz (Germany)</p>
Level	International/EU level
Description of the method / approach, the theory	<p>DEMOKLEOS acknowledges the vital and crucial role of education professionals in prevention and change and builds on the convergence of competences: specialist and subject-specific Democratic Competences, according to the model of the Council of Europe, need to be complemented by transversal skills and attitudes of pupils, such as leadership, e-democracy skills, citizenship skills, critical debating and learning to learn.</p> <p>DEMOKLEOS is prepared as a follow-up, according to a needs analysis, data collected and the demands of the teachers of all the participant partners to be better empowered to the politics of despair, straightly affecting the educational community in Europe.</p> <p>The DEMOKLEOS project has a multi-perspective, multi-level interactive and intercultural, experimental and experiential approach based on continuous interaction between all partners.</p> <p>The DEMOKLEOS project utilizes a "whole school approach" methodology that addresses democracy issues at a number of levels, from teacher competences and classroom methodologies to school ethics and governance and the contribution of community partnerships. The whole school approach can be considered the gold standard for mainstreaming democratic awareness in education.</p> <p>In practice, developing a "whole school" approach to democratic education means combining formal and non-formal teaching with opportunities for democratic experiences in the classroom and in the school in general, and strengthening the school's links with the wider community.</p> <p>Throughout the three years of the project, a succession of alternating periods of work conducted by the partners in their own environments - for design experimenting and disseminating - and general meetings to bring experiences together, to study quality evaluations, to draw conclusions and to decide on further developments.</p>

	<p>The project's methodology is blended learning based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online training using e-learning platforms. • In-class training. • Face-to-face training for teachers and school teachers organized by the host partners in different countries. • Workshops and exercises facilitated by the trained teachers. • Public seminars and Conferences in various countries to present the DEMOKLEOS outputs and products.
<p>Purpose / Goal</p>	<p>The objective of DEMOKLEOS is related to current challenges to which European school has to adopt a proactive attitude and handle Democratic Awareness and Collective Responsibility as a s ethic. Achieving this implies the need for a sustained dialogue about a whole school approach. DEMOKLEOS aligns with the realities of the 21st century, where citizens demand greater participation in public decision-making processes with the emergence of new information technologies and social networks.</p> <p>DEMOKLEOS commits strongly to European integration and a special concern for issues and their related areas such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political literacy • History / remembrance and Democracy in historical perspective in Europe • Critical debating about Teaching of controversial issues • Digital democracy • School democratic governance • Challenges of democratic schools in a globalized and pluralistic world • Human rights and a sustainable environment • Teacher professionalism on democratic key competences conflict and consensus: the project recognizes that divergence of opinion may be inherent enhanced school engagement and tools should provide opportunities for negotiation, mediation and consensus building. <p>Other goals of the DEMOKLEOS are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping democratic and anti-democratic attitudes in European school education and presenting a picture of the main populist and racist organisations operating in seven European countries • To analyse hate speech communication strategies in order to understand how populist organisations have used new media in recent years to spread their violent messages to younger generations • Deconstructing populist hate speech against the "other" and raising awareness of young people and minorities: deconstructing stereotypes about race, gender, disability and sexual orientation through analysis of media produced

	<p>by populist organisations and raising awareness of young people and minorities about how new media misrepresent them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth empowerment through e-participation: adopting a participatory and active approach to promote children's voice ownership and political literacy skills, in line with media literacy education perspectives that emphasize people empowerment over media censorship • To strengthen and increase the impact of the project, training for teachers on media literacy and populism/racism and the development of an online environment with resources on new media, hate speech against the "other" and racism
<p>Web link</p>	<p>https://dide-peiraia.att.sch.gr/index.php/menu-demokleos-about?view=article&id=5428:demokleos-about-eng&catid=122:eu-demokleo</p>
<p>References/ online sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demokleos Project Lesson Plans Link:https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pinY679_jSvGZdoKYq8dprqoFTA7eJiC/edit?usp=sharing&oid=109975392430691324954&rtpof=true&sd=true • DEMOKLEOS - Best Practices Manual on Democratic Key Competencies for Teacher Professionalism by Constantina Spiliotopoulou, Vinatsella Dimitra and Modeas Ioannis, 2018. Link:https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/0B8jgbsboar4JbmY0eWhCYzJpdms?resourcekey=0-iMVwqj4uDv8aLQ3yCrshWw • Classroom Activity: Rights and responsibilities in a Democracy Link:https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8jgbsboar4JOG45dWFpOUlaZkE/view?resourcekey=0-9lq_akZwXbZuVO4PR6BB9g • Classroom Activity: Training for Digital Democracy by Dr Dimakopoulou Alexandra, 2017. Link:https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8jgbsboar4JNTBKNjFvUmV4U3M/view?resourcekey=0-05qk7CILZWMtz6JDfslmA • Conference Paper: Encountering The "Politics of Fear": Teacher Training for A Media Propaganda Education to Prevent Political Extremism, In The Context of DEMOKLEOS, Erasmus+ KA2- Project by Constantina Spiliotopoulou, 2019. Link:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343632491_Encountering_The_Politics_of_FearTeacher_Training_for_A_Media_Propaganda_Education_to_Prevent_Political_Extremism_In_The_Context_of_DEMOKLEOS_Erasmus_KA2-Project

Best Practice 2: CARMA Project (EU Erasmus+)

<p>Place the logo of the project/ initiative or other image of the best practice</p>	
<p>Topic / Area</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Commission Erasmus+ KA2 Support to Policy Development and Cooperation
<p>Title</p>	<p>CARMA (RMA and other non-formal learning methods for Student Motivation)</p>
<p>Target group</p>	<p>The two direct target groups of the CARMA Project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers in reading, mathematics and science including teachers on an entry level and, Students aged 11 to 15 identified as disadvantaged, low achieving and at risk of early school leaving <p>Moreover, CARMA project addressed the following indirect target groups: teaching staff and professionals within school education, community of stakeholders in the policy making process i.e. parents, school service providers, civil society organisations and policy makers in school education.</p>
<p>Type</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lesson Plan/Learning Activity
<p>Date released</p>	<p>Project Starting date: 01/01/2016 Project Ending date: 30/06/2018</p>
<p>Partners / Network</p>	<p>CESIE (Italy, Coordinator) Uniersidad De Murcia (Spain) Pistes-Solidaires (France) Doğa Schools (Türkiye) UC Leuven (Belgium) Inovamais- Technological Innovation Consulting Services (Portugal) Verein Multikulturell (Austria)</p>
<p>Level</p>	<p>International/EU level</p>
<p>Description of the method / approach, the theory</p>	<p>The CARMA project introduce non-formal learning methods as a collaborative learning strategy to innovate school culture and transform classroom practices. The Project uses Reciprocal Maieutic Approach (RMA) as an inclusive assessment tool for increasing teachers' skills. The results achieved by the partnership were applied for pushing policies towards the inclusion of disadvantaged learners and reduce early school leaving.</p> <p>Within the scope of the project, 8 techniques, including P4C (Philosophy for Children), have been implemented and tested in face-to-face through the project workshop sessions by participating expert teachers.</p>

	<p>Philosophy for Children (P4C) is created by Matthew Lipman according to his Community of Inquiry Method (CoI) and it is practiced for a few decades in different countries. It is broadly defined as any group of individuals involved in a process of conceptual inquiry into problematic situations. In P4C sessions, children are not seen as passive perceivers of knowledge, but as active agents and as philosophers, who produce, criticize, and inquire a philosophical issue or a real life problem.</p>
<p>Purpose / Goal</p>	<p>The CARMA project foresees a consolidated process of proposing, enriching, and piloting an innovative learning approach. The Project's objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase student motivation and participation by offering new form of teaching-learning using non-formal approaches to support disadvantaged learners and increase their achievements. • To integrate the RMA as an assessment tool within school curricula. • To expand teachers' skills through training and assessment framework with knowledge and resources on how to use inclusive and participatory practices and develop collaborative relationships in and out of school. • To provide policy recommendations for strategies to reduce early school leaving and increase basic skills.
<p>Web link</p>	<p>https://carma-project.eu/</p>
<p>References/ Online sources</p>	<p>P4C Lesson Plan - Island Republic P4C Lesson Plan - The Culture of Democracy P4C Lesson Plan - Heinz's Dilemma P4C Lesson Plan - Light Pollution P4C Lesson Plan - Kindness P4C Teachers' Workshop 1 - Let's Create Philosophical Questions P4C Teachers' Workshop 2 - Philosophy for Kids P4C Teachers' Workshop 3 - The Pit of Inquiry</p>
<p>Additional notes</p>	<p>P4C Awareness Training Seminar - Professional Development Program of the Turkish Ministry of National Education</p> <p>Philosophy for Children (P4C) https://www.philosophy-foundation.org/p4c</p> <p>Montclair State University IAPC and SAPERE Institution are the institutions, which provide educational material for P4C pedagogy. Books of Matthew Lipman, Peter Worley, Jana Mohr Lone, Peter Worley, The Philosophy Foundation: https://www.philosophy-foundation.org/resources</p>

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European extension and updating**
ref. No 2023-2-DE04-KA220-YOU-000175190

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Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union